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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D6.2 Technical validation of the Pilot test environment and impact assessment of adopted innovations

CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission
AIPO	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
AIS	Automatic Identification System

CEDRE	Centralised European Data Reporting Environment
CRISTAL	Collaborative and Robust Innovations for Sustainable Transport Across Logistics
DAS	Data Acquisition System
DT	Digital Twin
EU	European Union
FOS	Fibre Optic Sensors
GA	Grant Agreement
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
IWT / IWW	Inland Waterway Transport / Inland Waterways
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
QR	Quick Response (Code)
RP	River Pilot
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
SB	Smart Buoys
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
UV	Ultraviolet
VNF	Voies Navigables de France

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1. Executive Summary

The “Technical validation of the pilot test environment and impact assessment of adopted innovations” report offers an general evaluation of the deployment and performance of CRISTAL's key technological solutions in real-life Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) conditions. The report assesses the innovations in operational environments, assessing their compatibility with infrastructure and capacity to contribute to the expected project-wide impacts as defined in the Grant Agreement.

The report begins by outlining the technical, environmental, and operational requirements of each CRISTAL innovation, including AE (Acoustic Emission), FOS (Fibre Optic Sensors), SIR (Subsurface Inspection Radar), Smart Buoys, SCMS (Synchmodal Corridor Management System), and Digital Twin. The description of the solutions serves as an introduction to further consideration of technical validation by comparing innovation requirements with the actual conditions present in the Polish, French, and Italian pilots.

Chapter 3 provides a description of each technology's installation, documenting the test environment, installation procedures, specific infrastructural constraints, and the challenges encountered. These insights are essential for understanding the maturity and adaptability of each solution under pilot-specific conditions.

Building upon this, Chapter 4 delivers a structured analysis of the innovations' impact on the operational and infrastructural dimensions of IWT, aligned with the seven Expected Impacts of the CRISTAL project. The report explores how the technologies improve waterway navigability, enhance infrastructure resilience, enable modal shift, reduce environmental footprint, and foster new governance models. The impact assessment methodology integrates internal self-evaluation by technology providers, internal workshops with pilot infrastructure operators, and a framework for external stakeholder validation to be reported in D6.3.

The document concludes with key lessons learned, guidance for external validation, and strategic recommendations for further deployment. It also presents a harmonised impact mapping and validation strategy that will support replication and scalability of CRISTAL innovations in other European IWT contexts.

In summary, the D6.2 Technical Validation and Impact Assessment report delivers a comprehensive view of how the CRISTAL technologies perform in real operational settings and how they align with the project's strategic goals for a more resilient, sustainable, and coordinated European transport system.

1.1. Introduction

D6.2 provides technical validation of the Pilot test environment and impact assessment of adopted innovations.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1: Alignment of D6.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D6.2 Technical validation of the Pilot test environment and impact assessment of adopted innovations	<i>Technical validation of the Pilot test environment</i>	Chapter 2, 3	The requirements for the technology in terms of its implementation in a river transport environment have been described. The requirements of the infrastructure and its managers that must be met in order to implement the technology in the selected test environment have been described.
	<i>Impact assessment of adopted innovations</i>	Chapter 5	A methodology for assessing the impact of technologies developed in the project on the achievement of the project objectives was presented. Methods and questions to be asked during the validation of the impact assessment of technologies on the project environment were presented.
	<i>Impact of the developed solutions to the test environment</i>	Chapter 3.4	The impact that the installation of technology may have on the infrastructure and environment of the IWW where the assembly takes place is presented.
TASKS			
Task 6.2 Installation and technical validation of the	<i>The infrastructure will be set up, configured and validated prior the pilot</i>	Chapter 3	The infrastructure has been set up, validated before the

Pilot test environment			technical innovations were set up on it.
	<i>Description of test procedures and the execution of acceptance tests</i>	Chapter 2, 3	The document includes a description of the procedures that technology providers had to follow for installation, as well as the requirements set by infrastructure managers to ensure the technologies could be safely and effectively deployed on-site.
	<i>Technical documentation of the infrastructure system will be developed including guidelines to enable effective service delivery, minimum hardware, to enable end-users from the Pilots to make use of the system.</i>	Chapter 2, 3	A description of the infrastructure system and documentation that technology providers had to provide (if required) to install the technology and present to infrastructure managers to ensure safe and effective implementation of the technology on site.
	<i>Guidelines to enable effective service delivery will be developed including physical requirements, minimum hardware, software</i>	Chapter 2, 3	Guidelines have been defined that must be met by both the technology and infrastructure for the correct installation of solutions on the infrastructure.
Task 6.3 Testing	<i>Developing the tests designed and planned in the previous task</i>	Chapter 3	Tests based on prior arrangements have been undertaken, and the essential conditions of installation and challenges have been described. A detailed description of the installation and pilot projects will be presented in WP2, WP7, WP8 and WP9.
	<i>Completion of a survey related to the impact of the tested solution on the environment</i>	Chapter 4	The internal study has been completed and the impact of the technology on the expected project results has been determined. The scope of

			the external study has been defined and its results will be presented in D6.3.
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1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable reports to the implementation of Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 within Work Package 6 (WP6) of the CRISTAL project. Its purpose is twofold: (1) to provide a detailed technical validation of pilot test environments established in Italy, France, and Poland, and (2) to assess the potential impact of the innovative technologies adopted to increase the climate resilience, reliability, and sustainability of inland waterway transport (IWT).

In line with the overall goal of CRISTAL — to enable a modal shift by increasing the IWT modal share by 20% and ensuring 50% operability even in extreme weather — this deliverable focuses on the assessment of four core technologies - CRISTAL innovations:

- **Acoustic Emission (AE)** : for real-time structural diagnostics,
- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)**: enabling distributed sensing along riverbank infrastructures,
- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)**: integrating multi-sensor data for predictive maintenance,
- **Smart Buoys (SB)**: acting as intelligent nodes for water level, flow, and traffic detection.

These solutions are deployed in various pilot environments and validated for installation feasibility, data interoperability, infrastructure resilience, and environmental compatibility.

In addition to these core solutions, the report also includes a concise technical validation and integration outlook for other innovative technologies developed or piloted within CRISTAL, including:

- **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)**: a digital platform designed to support dynamic coordination and optimisation of inland waterway logistics through integrated corridor monitoring, capacity management, and modal shift facilitation.
- **Digital Twin technologies (DT)**: enabling predictive simulation and virtual monitoring of infrastructure and operational scenarios to enhance decision-making and resilience planning.

This report assesses the core technological innovations developed within the CRISTAL project. Therefore, additional technologies implemented under the pilot's initiatives are not included in this document. Detailed technical descriptions and the results of these pilot innovations will be provided in the respective pilot work packages — WP7 (Italy), WP8 (France), and WP9 (Poland).

The structure of this report is as follows:

- **Chapter 2** outlines the general, technical, environmental, operational, and infrastructure requirements necessary for the installation and functioning of the key CRISTAL technologies across pilot environments.
- **Chapter 3** documents the technical validation of the test environments by comparing the available infrastructure against the previously defined requirements. It includes descriptions of each pilot setup, installation procedures, and identified gaps or limitations.
- **Chapter 4** provides an assessment of the operational and environmental impact of the implemented technologies. It presents the methodology and internal evaluation conducted with technology providers, as well as guidelines for stakeholder validation (to be further elaborated in D6.3).
- **Chapter 5** concludes the report by summarising key technical insights, outlining the next steps for impact validation, and offering recommendations for future deployment.

2. The requirements for setting up the CRISTAL technology in River Pilots

The CRISTAL sensor technologies developed within the CRISTAL project, and fully described in Deliverables D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3, have been installed in areas covered by river pilot activities. Each technology has its own specific characteristics and must be properly prepared for installation in order to carry out measurements. The installation requirements for individual sensor technologies can be organised into a set of structured guidelines. These guidelines address both the environmental conditions in which the technology is to be deployed and the practical aspects of equipment preparation, as well as the need for specialised tools, personnel, and maintenance. The specific characteristics of each technology are outlined based on the following categories:

- **General Requirements** - including surface and structure preparation, sensor protection, coupling and attachment methods, and routing and placement;
- **Technical Requirements** - specifying specific technical requirements, such as temperature and pressure tolerance, signal transmission requirements
- **Environmental Requirements** - indicating, where relevant, the environmental parameters necessary for proper installation, such as water quality (Water Quality), flow conditions, presence of sediment and debris (Sediment and Debris), accessibility and temperature extremes
- **Installation Times** - concerning the time required for installation of the technology and factors affecting the length of this process
- **Human Resources Needed** - describing the composition of the work team and the qualifications required of the personnel involved in the installation of the technology
- **Cost Considerations** - including an analysis of installation costs, including equipment costs (Equipment Costs), installation costs, maintenance costs and additional operating costs

Collecting this information allows the initial level of installation requirements to be determined, which must then be compared with the actual technological and environmental conditions at the sites where the technology is to be installed. This makes it possible to assess the realistic possibilities of implementing a given sensor technology in a test environment and to identify any additional work that may be necessary to enable installation and measurement.

Figure 1 CRISTAL solutions interconnections

Source: CRISTAL project presentation for Living Lab meeting

The basic technical, environmental and operational requirements that had to be met during the installation and integration of selected demonstration CRISTAL sensor technologies in pilot areas in Poland, Italy and France are presented further. The analysis covered four key technologies: acoustic emission (AE), fibre optic sensors (FOS), smart buoys (SB) and subsurface inspection radar (SIR) system.

Also requirements resulting from the specific nature of installation in a hydrotechnical environment, the need to ensure interoperability with existing IT systems, and the impact of local environmental conditions on the selection and installation of individual technologies have been considered. In addition, an overview of the general requirements for supporting technologies, such as the Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) and Digital Twin, is provided. Technologies falling within the scope of the individual River Pilots' own initiatives will be discussed in detail in documents prepared under WP7-WP9.

The following subsections describe in detail the technical and environmental requirements for technologies developed and tested in the CRISTAL project. Subsequently, the test environments will be validated, and the feasibility of effective installation of individual solutions in selected locations will be analysed.

2.1. Technical requirements for setting up AE

Acoustic emission (AE) technology is a passive monitoring method used to detect microcracks and structural damage in real time. It works by recording ultrasonic waves generated by material under stress, e.g., in concrete or steel hydraulic engineering structures. Thanks to its high sensitivity and continuous operation, AE can effectively support predictive maintenance activities for water infrastructure.

Figure 2: Acoustic Emission devices on the infrastructure

Source: CERTH own elaboration

The installation of Acoustic Emission (AE) sensors involves specific requirements to ensure effective monitoring and accurate data collection, the key ones being presented further.

General requirements

The acoustic emission (AE) system used in this project is based on a rugged and portable AE micro-SHM recorder with four channels. The recorder runs on internal batteries and is capable of sampling acoustic signals up to 400 kHz. Piezoelectric sensors (PZTs) of two types were used to detect the signals: three R15a sensors with a bandwidth of 60 to 170 kHz and one R6a sensor operating between 10 and 80 kHz.

PZT sensors must be mounted on clean, smooth, flat surfaces to ensure proper sensor coupling and accurate signal transmission. Before mounting, any contaminants such as rust, paint, oils or dirt should be removed using fine sandpaper or other abrasive cleaning methods. The surface should also be thoroughly dried to eliminate moisture that can interfere with acoustic conductivity.

A coupling material should be used between the sensor and the structural surface to enhance acoustic energy transmission. Suitable materials include silicone grease, epoxy resin or petroleum jelly. If epoxy resin is used, a thin and evenly distributed layer is crucial to avoid trapping air gaps that could interfere with signal purity.

For long-term installations, it is crucial to maintain the integrity of the coupling medium over time. This is achieved by encapsulating the sensor in an external microsite housing, which is then attached to the structure with adhesive. This housing prevents leakage or degradation of the coupling medium. Depending on the construction material and operational needs, different mounting methods can be used - such as magnetic mounts for ferromagnetic surfaces, epoxy bonding for permanent installation or mechanical clamps and screws for temporary or repositionable configurations.

Correct sensor orientation is essential for optimal monitoring. Sensors should be positioned according to the expected direction of acoustic emission, usually perpendicular to likely crack propagation paths. This orientation ensures accurate location and characterisation of defects.

Technical requirements

To confirm that the surface preparation and connector quality meet operational standards, an automatic sensor test procedure (AST) must be carried out. This involves placing a reference sensor close to the sensor

under test and generating pulses that simulate acoustic events. The response is then analysed to verify correct signal transmission. Alternatively, a calibrated pulse generator can be used to check system sensitivity and signal purity.

The selection of appropriate control points on the monitored gate structure is a key part of the implementation process. It starts with a comprehensive assessment of the gateway geometry and its operational role. Depending on the type of expected failures - such as microcrack formation, piston degradation, trench precipitation or the impact of a loose object - sensors need to be placed within a 1 metre radius of potential failure zones. The number and type of sensors, as well as the required AE recorder (from 4 to 32 channels), will depend on the number of monitoring points needed and the specific frequencies associated with the failure modes. For example:

- Micro-crack detection requires sensors with a bandwidth of 60 to 170 kHz,
- Piston-related signals are best detected with sensors in the 10 to 80 kHz range,
- Precipitation monitoring in pits typically uses sensors between 20 and 60 kHz,

When detecting bouncing debris or objects, the maximum effective distance is up to 4 metres from the sensor.

Shielded coaxial cables must be used to reduce electromagnetic interference, and preamplifiers should be ideally embedded in the sensor housing to increase durability and reduce signal loss. Cables should be installed in such a way as to allow the monitored gateway or infrastructure elements to move freely without causing stress or mechanical strain.

Ensure that the sensor mounting method does not compromise the structural integrity of the surface to be monitored. In addition, all installations must comply with electrical safety standards. This includes proper earthing and isolation of power and data lines. If the AE recorder is powered by a standard socket, it is recommended that a smart socket is used to allow remote power disconnection in the event of a system fault or failure.

Environmental Requirements

Environmental protection measures are essential, especially in harsh environments. Sensors should be resistant to weather conditions and temperature extremes. In the event of heavy rainfall or high humidity, both sensors and data logger should be enclosed in weather-sealed housings. Additional precautions may be needed in corrosive or industrial environments.

The effective functioning of an acoustic emission (AE) system depends on several critical environmental factors that must be considered during the planning and installation stages. AE sensors are designed to operate over a wide temperature range, typically -40°C to 120°C, although this range may vary depending on the sensor model. High-temperature sensors or a protective heat shield should be used in areas where temperatures may exceed these limits.

Humidity and moisture levels are also essential factors. In environments exposed to high humidity or direct exposure to water, it is essential to use waterproof or weatherproof sensors - preferably with an IP65 or IP67 rating. Connectors used to mount sensors must be adequately sealed to prevent moisture from entering the contact area and degrading signal quality.

In environments where dust or airborne contaminants are present, sensors should be protected by suitable housings or covers to prevent the build-up of contaminants that can affect performance. Routine cleaning may be necessary to ensure continued measurement accuracy.

Vibration and background noise can significantly affect the reliability of AE measurements. Installation should aim to minimise exposure to these noises through appropriate sensor placement and, where necessary, the use of signal filtering techniques. Sensors with high signal-to-noise ratios may also be selected for environments with constant mechanical activity.

Electromagnetic interference (EMI) is another factor that can affect data quality. AE systems should be installed away from strong EMI sources such as high-voltage lines or electric motors to mitigate such interference. In addition, shielded cables and adequate grounding are recommended to protect signal integrity.

Finally, the accessibility of the installation site should be considered. All sensors and system components should be placed in locations that will remain accessible for future maintenance, inspection or troubleshooting. If the target location is remote or restricted, appropriate access strategies should be planned in advance, such as removable hatches, platforms, or remote data access.

Installation Times

The time required to install an acoustic emission (AE) system varies depending on the scale of deployment and the environmental and structural conditions at the site. For small-scale configurations, such as the installation of a single set of four AE sensors, the process typically takes around one hour. This includes surface preparation, sensor installation and system calibration.

For a more extensive multi-sensor network installed on a small hydraulic structure, the entire configuration can usually be completed in half a day or a full day. The total time required depends primarily on the number of sensors being deployed and the complexity of the site layout.

Several factors can affect the installation time. Surface conditions play a key role - rough, corroded or contaminated surfaces can significantly lengthen the preparation phase. The type of sensor used also affects the timeline; permanently installed sensors, which require epoxy bonding, typically require longer installation times than temporary sensors using magnetic mounts or clamps. Environmental challenges, such as adverse weather conditions, limited visibility or confined spaces, can also lead to delays, making access and work difficult or unsafe.

Proper planning and on-site assessment prior to deployment are essential to minimise time risks and ensure efficient system installation.

Human Resources Needed

The successful installation of an acoustic emission (AE) system requires a multidisciplinary team with clearly defined roles. Typically, the team consists of one to two technicians responsible for the preparation of the sensor mounting surface and the physical installation of the sensors in the infrastructure. In addition, one engineer must oversee the design of the sensor system, perform system calibration and verify correct data acquisition through test procedures.

In environments with specific hazards, such as working at heights or in confined spaces, dedicated safety personnel must also be present to ensure compliance with health and safety regulations.

All members of the team should have the appropriate qualifications tailored to their tasks. As a minimum, technicians should receive basic training in non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques with a particular focus on acoustic emission systems. In addition, all personnel involved in on-site work must have valid safety training certificates, including instruction on working at height and entering confined or restricted spaces.

Cost Considerations

Implementing an acoustic emission (AE) system involves several expenditure categories. Equipment costs vary depending on the type and scale of installation. AE sensors, which are reusable, typically range from €500 to €2,500 per unit, depending on their sensitivity and specifications. Pre-amplifiers, also reusable, cost between €300 and €1,500 apiece. The data acquisition system (DAS) represents a significant investment, with prices ranging from €5,000 to €20,000, depending on the number of channels and advanced features. Additional accessories such as acoustic connectors, signal cables (which are usually reusable) and sensor mounting components can cost between €100 and €1,500.

Installation costs are mainly influenced by labour and site-specific preparations. The cost of a technician is usually between €50 and €100 per hour per person. In cases where the installation site requires surface cleaning, scaffolding or special access conditions, additional costs of €500 to €2,000 may apply.

Maintenance costs include periodic calibration of the system, which can range from €1,500 to €2,500 per year, especially if the AE system is to remain permanently installed in the infrastructure. Sensor replacement is carried out as necessary, depending on environmental conditions and wear and tear.

There may also be additional costs in specific cases, such as travel costs for installations in remote locations. In addition, permits or specialised safety equipment may be required when deploying the system in regulated or hazardous environments.

2.2. Technical requirements for setting up FOS

Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS) are advanced monitoring tools generally used to measure physical parameters such as strain, temperature, and water depth with high precision. They are particularly well-suited for harsh and aquatic environments due to their immunity to electromagnetic interference, durability, and ability to operate over long distances. In the context of inland waterway infrastructure, FOS technology is considered to monitor critical elements like sluices, bridge piers, and riverbeds, supporting long-term asset management and predictive maintenance. In CRISTAL Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS) are employed for the advanced, real-time and continuous monitoring of the navigability conditions in free-flowing waterways.

Figure 3 FOS technology devices

Source: ENEA own elaboration

General requirements

FOS is procured as a fully engineered, ready-to-be-installed component. FOS is a monitoring system having the aspect of a large metallic waterproof sealed box instrumented with fibre optic sensors. Both the side and the bottom surfaces of FOS are massive and have structural functions only, whereas the upper surface (referred to as the weighing surface) has controlled elastic properties and performs the weighing function according to the 'bending plate' operation principle. FOS is to be installed in the riverbed to estimate the height of the debris deposit and thus the decrease of the water depth useful for navigation. FOS operates as an immersed weighing system, enabling the calculation of the height of the sediment column accumulating in free-flowing waterways on its surface, based on its weight and predicted density.

Materials and construction techniques of procured FOS shall comply with underwater long-term installation; special requirements shall be required for installation sites with special environmental and water chemical conditions.

Procured FOS are instrumented with fibre optic sensors. The fibre optic sensors are installed and enclosed in the waterproof, sealed structure of FOS itself, and thus are intrinsically protected. The fibre optic sensors shall be calibrated and qualified for operating in the temperature range expected in the installation site, duly overestimated for exceptional events.

FOS shall be installed submerged, in a stable geometric condition. A civil engineering work is required in the form of a stable concrete basement with a flat upper surface facing upward. FOS shall be housed recessed in the basement, being the FOS weighing surface at the same level as the basement's upper surface. At installation time, the weighing surface of FOS shall be free and exposed to the future accumulation of debris.

The civil engineer work shall be planned with the necessary geo- and hydro-considerations pertinent to the installation site. The stability of the structure is a prerequisite and shall consider all possible waterway

maintenance works. Marine-grade clamps, adhesives, or fasteners resistant to water corrosion shall be considered in securing FOS on the basement.

At installation time, the level of the weighing surface shall correspond to the reference riverbed level. The reference riverbed level is the deepest possible level taken into account for navigability, either natural or artificially produced and regularly maintained.

- In the case of a stable riverbed level, the reference riverbed level corresponds to it. The concrete basement shall be made as a foundation with an excavation in the river bed. The presence of FOS will not alter the natural depth of the water.
- In case of an unstable riverbed level, dredging shall be considered to have the concrete basement's upper surface at the reference riverbed level. Within periods of 'natural waterbed lowering', the presence of the FOS will constitute a permanent rising of the natural depth of the water, but: i) that permanent rising will not reduce the maximum water depth considered for the navigability; ii) installing FOS at the quota of a temporarily lowered riverbed, would cause a future burring of FOS and its overall working efficiency decrease.

Routing of cables shall respect standard prescription for telecommunication fiber optic cabling. Cables shall be laid with an armoured shield or inserted in protection conduits. Possible damage from flowing water, debris, human activities and wildlife must be considered. Cables, cabling works and cable junctions shall comply with telecommunication standards. DAS units shall be positioned in dry, secure locations with environmental controls. DAS shall support remote monitoring and local real-time data pre-processing for alarm management.

Technical Requirements

The type of sensor technology selected depends on the measurement needs. Point sensors are ideal for detecting localised changes in strain or temperature, which are common indicators of structural stress or damage.

All FOS units should be rated for the environmental conditions expected in inland waterway systems. This includes operating temperatures typically ranging between 0°C and 40°C. Pressure-rated sensors are necessary for deeper or high-flow installations to withstand increased hydraulic forces.

Single-mode optical fibres are recommended for effective signal transmission over long distances due to their low signal attenuation. Connections between fibres should be fusion-spliced to ensure optimal performance and reduce signal loss.

The Data Acquisition System (DAS) associated with the FOS network should be installed in secure, dry locations with stable environmental conditions. The DAS must support remote access and real-time monitoring capabilities, allowing operators to track sensor readings without needing to access the site physically—an essential feature for challenging or remote installations.

Environmental Requirements

Materials shall suit the requirements concerning the water chemical (freshwater, brackish, saltwater) of the installation site, to provide resistance to corrosion and general degradation.

The civil engineering infrastructures shall withstand the water flow and potential impacts of materials drawn by the current, the natural riverbed variations. In the installation site selection, access for maintenance and inspection of the installation shall be considered. Materials and FOS's fiber optic sensors shall have working temperatures within the predictable most extreme changes.

Installation Times

Installation time can vary largely according to the geo- and hydro-technical conditions of the installation site. The use of special fast-curing concrete and precast components can lower construction time. Team composition shall consider commonly skilled yard workers, and might need personnel for marine and diving operations.

Installation of FOS on the completed concrete basement, and cable laying in the prepared conduits can be estimated from three to five days, but particular conditions could expand the necessary time. Team composition shall consider fibre optic networking technicians and might need personnel for marine and diving operations.

Special conditions: Greater depth and faster currents can call for special solutions and longer times.

Human Resources Needed

The successful deployment of Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) systems necessitates a multidisciplinary team equipped with specific expertise and certifications. Typically, the installation team comprises two to three technicians responsible for tasks such as sensor installation, cable routing, and surface preparation. These technicians ensure that the physical components of the system are correctly installed and secured.

An engineer is also integral to the team, overseeing the design of the system, calibrating sensors, and conducting quality control to ensure that the system functions as intended. In scenarios where sensors are to be installed in deeper waters or submerged locations, a specialised diving team is required to carry out the underwater installation processes safely and effectively.

The personnel involved must possess a solid understanding of fiber optic systems and data acquisition methods. Familiarity with marine or waterway environments is crucial, as it enables the team to anticipate and mitigate challenges unique to such settings. Moreover, team members should hold relevant safety certifications, particularly for working in aquatic environments. This includes certifications for diving operations and confined space entry, ensuring that all activities are conducted in compliance with safety regulations and best practices.

Cost Considerations

The investment in Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) systems encompasses several components, each contributing to the overall expenditure. Engineered FOS units typically range in cost from €10,000 to €35,000, depending on their specifications and capabilities. The cabling required for these systems varies based on the installation environment; for land-based installations, the cost is approximately €1.50 per meter, while submerged installations incur higher costs, around €5.00 per meter, due to the need for specialised materials and protective measures. The Data Acquisition System (DAS), a critical component for data collection and processing, is priced between €15,000 and €35,000, reflecting its complexity and the level of integration required.

Installation costs for FOS systems can vary significantly, influenced by factors such as the site's environmental conditions and the necessity for specialised equipment, particularly in marine settings where diving operations may be required. These variables make it challenging to provide a standardised installation cost, as each project may present unique challenges and requirements.

Maintenance is an ongoing consideration for FOS systems. Annual inspections of the installed sensors and submarine cables are essential to ensure system integrity and performance, with costs estimated between €1,000 and €3,000, depending on the accessibility of the installation and prevailing environmental conditions. Periodic calibration is also necessary to maintain measurement accuracy. This process, which may involve the use of known weights operated by a crane vessel, is estimated to cost between €1,000 and €3,000 annually.

Over time, components of the FOS system may require replacement due to wear and tear. However, with proper maintenance, these systems are designed to have a working life of approximately 10 years, providing long-term monitoring solutions for various applications.

2.3. Technical requirements for setting up SIR

The Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) system developed in the CRISTAL project for being deployed in the French pilot was designed for in-depth scanning of critical IWW structures, such as locks, dams, etc., to identify subsurface features of interest that may be the results of potential damages, which could further develop into critical failures. Regular inspections carried out with the SIR system would allow collecting relevant data, which would enable the health monitoring of inspected assets over longer periods of time. By continuously monitoring parameters such as strain, vibration, temperature, and displacement, SIR systems enable early detection of potential issues, facilitating proactive maintenance and ensuring structural integrity. This proactive approach not only enhances public safety by preventing catastrophic failures but also optimizes maintenance schedules, reduces repair costs, and extends the service life of infrastructure. The radar system does not require special permission to install the technology on the lock infrastructure as the lock was emptied for another purpose and VNF took the opportunity to have the lock wall and nearby ground surveyed.

Figure 4 SIR technology

Source: EUMO own elaboration

General Requirements

The subsurface radar inspection is constructed with a Modular Operating Platform and this is the physical apparatus providing the system structure and operability through electromechanical functionalities. The bespoke Mechanical Super-structure manufactured resembles a large XY Plotter, and comprises a rigid vertical metal framework standing parallel to the lock wall, containing a motorised drive mechanism to advance the radar measurement antenna steadily across the survey quadrant, while maintaining a fixed lift-off from the contact surface, sufficiently high to circumvent potential collision with the undulating wall face, but sufficiently low to minimise energy loss and in turn yield clearer subsurface imagery.

The operation of the SIR system does not require any surface treatment or preparation as the antenna never touches the surface with the lift being about 50mm.

The main equipment on the platform is the Subsurface Radar Unit, which comprises a monostatic 1GHz Zond radar antenna, the Zond 12e Advanced Radar Controller and a Windows Slave PC. The Zond antenna is self-contained and protected.

The Modular Operating Platform also includes the Power Unit and electrical housings for the onboard electrical systems, which enable the measurement and control equipment to function. Therefore, there is a requirement for mains power provision, which is available at all prospective inspection sites. However, contingencies for a primary Power Unit utilising a rechargeable battery array are being considered, with the option for a battery bypass input to enable the apparatus to be directly run of mains electric, if available onsite. Considering the specific power requirements for each component and sub-assembly of the platform, the SIR technology will require power supply providing 220-249V at 50Hz.

The Modular Operating Platform will be positioned by a crane capable of lifting 300kg, to allow for placement on different locations on the lock wall.

Technical Requirements

The Subsurface inspection system operates reliably at temperatures between -20°C to 60°C . The pressure value is irrelevant to SIR operation.

Configuration and interfacing of the Geolocation Unit) and Subsurface Radar Unit is required preliminary testing of hardware setup and network connections between the zBELL RTK GNSS geolocation antenna and Zond 12e Advanced Radar Controller to ensure effective communication between both elements during data acquisition.

The main non-functional requirements for the installation and operation of the SIR system are listed below.

The inspection system should be adaptable to work for different use cases associated to different types of lock and dams.

- The inspection system should be transportable in a LGV and the components manually movable.
- It should be possible to setup and dismantle the system within a reasonable timeframe.
- Scan Parameter Adjustment. It should be possible for onsite operators to customise scan settings in reasonable time.

- Emergency Stop. It shall be possible to fully halt the apparatus in the event of emergency with a single button push.
- It should be possible onsite to track progress of the inspection (across quadrant and across full lock) 'at a glance' from the system interface.

The internal power supply of the apparatus shall be sufficient to power it for a typical work shift, and be rechargeable overnight.

More details have been considered for the assessment and technical validation of the technology and are presented in the deliverable report D10.1 Validation of the CRISTAL project using the Validation Framework.

Environmental Requirements

The environmental conditions for the subsurface radar control system are as follows:

- Factors such as water quality and flow conditions are not relevant to the operation of the system, as the water level in the lock must be as low as possible before testing. Similarly, considerations regarding sediment and contamination are not applicable, given that the water level is minimised before testing and there is no requirement to enter the lock.
- The modular operating platform has been designed to be attached to a crane with a lifting capacity of 300 kg, allowing it to be positioned precisely on the lock wall. Therefore, access to a crane near the lock wall is necessary.
- The subsurface inspection system operates effectively within an internal temperature range of -20°C to 60°C, with the main limitation being the electronic components.
- Climate immunity. The inspection system shall be able to operate in the lock environment, regardless the weather and other environmental conditions.
- The inspection system shall have an appropriate Ingress Protection level (min IP65), so that it could operate in lock environment
- The radar-based system shall comply with radar frequency regulations.

Installation Times

The Modular Operating Platform is transported on to two pallets and with two cases containing electronics. It takes 2 hours after delivery for 2 engineers to build the Modular Operating Platform. It can then be moved into place at the lock side by a forklift. The Modular Operating Platform is then attached to a crane capable of lifting 300kg to allow for placement on the lock wall. Placement on the lock wall requires a qualified crane driver and a qualified crane guide to accurately position the platform on the lock wall. The crane hold the platform near the lock wall throughout the inspection.

Human Resources Needed

Implementing the system requires a multidisciplinary team with specialized skills to ensure effective deployment and operation. The core team typically comprises two engineers responsible for assembling the Modular Operating Platform and overseeing the technical aspects of the system. A qualified crane operator and a crane guide are essential for safely positioning the platform on the lock wall. During the inspection phase, an experienced radar operator conducts the subsurface scans, while another engineer manages the positioning and records the datasets. Additional personnel may include a forklift driver for transporting equipment and a health and safety officer to ensure compliance with safety protocols. Each team member plays a critical role in successfully implementing and operating the SHM system.

Cost Considerations

The implementation of SIR systems involves several cost considerations:

The initial investment in SIR equipment typically ranges from €20,000 to €25,000. This includes the cost of sensors, data acquisition systems, and related equipment for monitoring structural integrity.

The configuration and implementation of an SIR system is estimated at around €2,000. This includes labour costs, equipment deployment and integration with existing structures.

Annual maintenance, which includes routine checks, system calibration and potential minor repairs, is expected to amount to approximately €2,000. Regular maintenance ensures the longevity and accuracy of the SIR system.

There are additional expenses to consider, such as travel to the test site and personnel accommodation during the installation and maintenance phases. These costs may vary depending on the location and duration of the project.

It is important to note that while these figures provide a general overview, actual costs may vary depending on specific project requirements, structural complexity, and regional economic factors. Furthermore, investing in SIR systems can lead to long-term savings by enabling proactive maintenance, reducing the likelihood of serious structural failures and associated repair costs.

2.4. Technical requirements for setting up Smart Buoys

Smart buoys are advanced floating devices designed to monitor water environments in real time. Equipped with various sensors, they can collect data on water quality parameters such as temperature, pH and turbidity, as well as environmental conditions such as wind speed and current speed. The buoys are securely anchored in waterways, near bridges or river banks, and transmit the collected data via a GSM network to centralised servers for analysis. The buoys have a communication module with the vessel, which allows them to record the passage of ships or barges on the waterway. This is particularly important if waterways, as in Poland, are not equipped with a RIS system.

Figure 5 Smart Buoy devices

Source: L-PIT own elaboration

General Requirements

The sensors and electronics of smart buoys and the power source should be installed in a separate, sealed compartment or use sensors designed for use in water. Use waterproof sealants designed for use in water and, if necessary, apply a UV-resistant marine sealant.

The radar sensor mounted on the bridge should protect its electronics in a sealed, weatherproof box or cabinet with sealed doors and a drain for condensed water.

The buoy should be anchored with a reinforced anchor and chain (or stainless steel cable) of a weight appropriate to the size of the submerged part of the buoy. The solution used in the design is a buoy with a diameter of 700 mm and a reinforced anchor weighing 110 kg, with a chain length of 10 m. The forces resulting from the resistance of the Smart Buoy body to the river current must also be considered.

To position the buoy on the river, it should be anchored from a motorboat that can be easily transported on a road trailer. It has an engine powerful enough to stop in the current and gently lower the buoy with the anchor into the water.

The radar sensor system connected to the river buoys should be installed on the bridge railing, where the radar sensor for measuring the distance from the water surface should be placed. The sensor should be mounted using easy-to-remove brackets and clamps. Ensure that the sensor protrudes beyond the structural elements of the bridge span so that the radar beam emitted by the sensor is in contact with the river surface. Required angle of the radar beam relative to the water surface: 90 degrees Required minimum projection of the radar sensor beyond the edge of the bridge: 0.5 m

The selected sensor mounting method must not perforate or damage any of the bridge structure elements. The location of the sensor on the bridge structure and the mounting of the sensor must not interfere with the existing traffic organisation on the bridge.

Technical Requirements

The Smart Buoy system is designed to operate in specific environmental conditions. Measurements should only be taken at air temperatures between 0°C and 50°C and water temperatures above zero. In addition, the system requires a stable and active GSM signal for real-time data transmission.

As part of the installation process, technicians must check the effectiveness of data transfer between the installed sensors and the central server to ensure smooth communication during operation.

Environmental Requirements

The Smart Buoy system has been designed to work effectively in low salinity water environments, and the water purity class does not affect measurement accuracy. The measurement conditions are assumed to include river currents of up to 2 metres per second and may also include local backwater effects, particularly near river mouths where fresh water meets the sea.

To ensure reliable operation, a minimum water depth of 0.7 metres is required, and during measurements the system should operate within a wind speed range of 0 to 10 metres per second. It is very important that there is no large floating debris in the water body, such as logs, tree branches or other solid objects that may appear during seasonal or tidal phenomena in rivers, as they can hit the anchored buoy with great force and damage the buoy structure or sensors.

With regard to temperature conditions, measurements should not be taken when the water temperature falls below 0.5°C or the ambient air temperature falls below zero, as such extreme conditions may affect the performance of the equipment or the reliability of the data. The system should also be installed in easily accessible locations to ensure safe and efficient implementation and maintenance.

Installation Times

The typical time required for the installation or removal of five smart buoys is approximately two days. In contrast, the installation or removal of two radar sensors on bridges usually takes one day. These estimates are based on several logistical assumptions, including a maximum road distance of 350 kilometres to the furthest installation site, high-quality road infrastructure availability, and paved boat launching sites along the riverbank. In addition, the installation plan assumes that the motorboat used to deploy the buoys can be transported on a trailer and launched near the designated mooring locations.

The total duration of the installation work may be extended due to various factors. Increased distance to the mooring points of the smart buoys may significantly extend the installation time, as may limited access to the river or difficult weather conditions. Adverse weather conditions, such as thick fog, heavy rain or strong winds, may delay installation and temporarily prevent work from being carried out on the river or bridge.

In addition, administrative procedures must be taken into account in the schedule. Approximately one month should be allocated to obtain all the necessary permits from the relevant authorities: Polish Water Authority

for the placement of smart buoys and the Road and Bridge Authority for installing radar sensors on bridge structures.

Human Resources Needed

Installing Smart Buoys on inland waterways requires a coordinated effort from a specialised team. A crew of two to three people is necessary to deploy buoys on the river. This team must have access to transport and a motorboat mounted on a trailer, allowing for efficient movement between anchorage points. The recommended personnel includes an Inland Navigation Captain, responsible for navigating the motorboat and ensuring the buoys are anchored in compliance with relevant regulations; a technician to manage the physical anchoring of the buoys; and an engineer to verify data transmission between the sensors and the central server.

Two individuals with appropriate transport are typically sufficient to install radar sensors on bridges. This smaller team should include an engineer, tasked with installing the sensor and confirming its data transmission capability, and a technician or second engineer responsible for physically assembling the equipment and coordinating with road and bridge management authorities.

In some cases, particularly when dealing with multiple buoys or challenging environmental conditions, it may be advantageous to engage a specialised service provider. These companies can offer on-water installation services using well-equipped vessels, experienced crews, and all necessary logistics to ensure compliant and efficient deployment.

Cost Considerations

The implementation of the intelligent buoy system involves several categories of costs. The total cost of equipment, including buoys, sensors, electronic components and auxiliary infrastructure, is estimated at €40,000- €60,000.

Installation costs associated with the deployment of buoys and radar sensors are estimated at approximately €5,600 and include labour, transport and specialised tools or vessels for deployment.

Maintenance costs, which include routine inspections, servicing and minor repairs of both buoys and bridge-mounted sensors, are estimated at approximately €6,800 per year.

In addition to the above costs, there are additional costs related to logistics, such as travel costs to and from the test site and accommodation costs for the technical team during the installation and testing period. These costs may vary depending on the location and duration of the field work.

2.5. Technical requirements for setting up Digital Twin (DT)

General requirements

The three Digital Twins (DTs) are digital systems, currently hosted in hardware infrastructure located in the Fraunhofer Institute for Material Flow and Logistics in Dortmund. These are accessible online and connected to the project's data broker. In principle, it is also possible to install all three DTs separately locally or on other

servers, for example in a Docker environment. However, as this is a system that integrates technology, the requirements for its operation will be presented in the following paragraphs.

Technical requirements

As the digital twins can also be installed locally, e.g., on a laptop, there are basically no major requirements that need to be observed. The system is scalable overall, which means that the more instances are running, e.g. a number of sheds, the more capacity is required. For the first phase, 'standard' laptops are completely sufficient. Example:

- Windows Operating System
- 32GB RAM
- Intel I9-10885H
- 1TB Hard Disc
- 1Gbps Ethernet connection

The data is mainly provided directly by the user, comes directly from AIPo (historical water levels) or comes from the Data Broker (sensor data). In principle, the DTs are also technically executable without data, but of course not useful. In particular, data from intelligent buoys, such as sensor data and GPS localisation, are required for the Digital Twin Buoys. For the Digital Twin Water Level, historical water levels and weather data are required to train the models. For the Digital Twin Locks, information such as length, width, height of locks and, above all, data from the AE system and SIR are required.

Safety considerations and environmental requirements

Given that the DT system are a digital system installed indoors, thus not having any physical activities for its installation, maintenance and operation in the open environment, there are no specific safety considerations or environmental requirements. Of course there are security mechanisms for accessing and authenticating the systems.

Installation time

The time that was required for the development of the three Digital Twin systems (hardware setup, algorithmic development of functionalities, connection to external systems, development of the User Interface, testing) in the context of the CRISTAL project was just over two years of development time. As the sensor suppliers have been slow to respond, there are still around two months of development time to go.

As a centralised system installed at Fraunhofer IML headquarters, DT does not require installation at the end user's location.

Human resources needed

Since the system is an online platform that end users access with a password/login details, installation at the end user's location just means logging in to the platform. No extra hardware needs to be installed at the end user's location. At least one user should be trained in the use of the platform and its functionality, which may take no more than 1 day.

Cost estimation

Since, as described above, the installation can be very diverse, it is hardly possible to provide valid information here. The personnel costs for ongoing operation should correspond to the usual support costs, as the systems are stable once installed. Based on a normal server infrastructure, you can perhaps roughly assume the following:

- Approx. €10.000 (one-time) initial for hardware and peripherals costs
- Approx. €300 (monthly) for energy costs

2.6. Technical requirements for setting up Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)

General requirements

SCMS is a centralised digital system (online platform), currently installed in hardware infrastructure located in CERTH's premises in Thessaloniki (i.e. the central building of the Hellenic Institute of Transport). Therefore, there is no need for a separate installation of hardware components of the system in the river areas that are or will be included and served by the SCMS. However, as this is a system that integrates technology, the requirements for its operation will be presented in the following paragraphs.

Technical requirements

Regarding the specific technical requirements of the SCMS and based on the current installation, the SCMS platform requires to be hosted on a server machine with the following minimal specifications:

- Ubuntu 24.04 operating system
- 64GB RAM
- Intel Xeon CPU
- 1TB NVMe SSD
- 1Gbps Ethernet connection

The server will be placed inside a server room with a cooling system, a power backup (UPS and generator), and secured access.

With respect to the installation and operation of the system to a river area, the process mainly involves ensuring the integration of the SCMS with external data sources as well as the flow of the minimum required data concerning the operation of river transport, so that the system can provide its services (i.e. the early info and alert, the route planning assessment, the toolbox of services and the observatory functionalities). More specifically, this data includes:

- **River geographical information:** Provide the river's, and for all other relevant navigable segments like river canals, geographical information in GeoJSON format.

- **River navigability information:** Provide information related to which types of barge/vessels can navigate through each segment of the river (following the EU classification of rivers¹ regarding maximum draught, length, beam and minimum bridge clearance).
- **Ports & intermodal terminals coordinates:** Provide the WGS84/GPS coordinates of all the river ports and any significant intermodal land terminals that may exist along the river's corridor.
- **Infrastructure information:** Provide infrastructure-related information for locks and bridges:
 - **Locks:** WGS84/GPS coordinates, wait times/schedule
 - **Bridges:** WGS84/GPS coordinates, bridge clearance, wait times/schedule (for moving bridges)
- **Railway information:** Provide railway geographical information along the river corridor in GeoJSON format including links with river ports/terminals along with rail fixed schedules for cargo transportations from the relevant railway authorities/ organizations.
- **Notices to Skippers (NtS):** Provide APIs with Notices to Skippers info from local government authorities or regulatory organizations that can be consumed from the SCMS platform.
- **Navigability/disruption/weather data:** Provide APIs with alerts info related to navigability/disruption events/weather from local government authorities or relevant organizations that can be consumed from the SCMS platform.

Safety considerations and environmental requirements

Given that SCMS is a digital system installed indoors, thus not having any physical activities for its installation, maintenance and operation in the open environment (including the river ecosystems), there are no specific safety considerations or environmental requirements.

Installation time

The time that was required for the development of the SCMS system (hardware setup, algorithmic development of functionalities, connection to external systems, development of the User Interface, testing) in the context of the CRISTAL project was approximately two years. With respect to the implementation of the system in a (new) river area, given that the required data as well as the connections to data sources are available, it is estimated at approximately two months.

As a centralised system installed at CERTH's headquarters, SCMS does not require installation at the end user's location.

Human resources needed

Since the system is an online platform that end users access with a password/login details, installation at the end user's location just means logging in to the platform. No extra hardware needs to be installed at the end user's location. At least one user should be trained in the use of the platform and its functionality, which may take no more than 1 day.

¹ Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (1992). *Resolution No. 92/2 on new classification of inland waterways* (CEMT/CM(92)6/FINAL). OECD.

Cost estimation

A rough estimation of the main cost items associated with the SCMS' software development, hardware components (considering future upgrades/expansion of the system) and the system operation and maintenance is the following:

- Approx. €15.000 (one-time) for hardware and peripherals costs
- Approx. €1.500 (monthly) for external APIs/services subscriptions
- Approx. €300 (monthly) for energy costs
- Approx. €150.000 (yearly) for personnel costs

2.7. Pilots own initiatives

In addition to the main technologies tested within the CRISTAL project, **each pilot site has also proposed and tested its own additional initiatives** aimed at enhancing the resilience, sustainability, and operational efficiency of inland waterway transport. These initiatives include, among others, the implementation of Cold Ironing systems, Smart Bulletin boards, CEDRE freight data optimization technology, Geolocation systems for barges without AIS, French Smart Buoys for improved waterway management, and the organization of pilot voyages in Polish river sections.

Each of these initiatives is being technically validated in relation to its installation and operational environment, with a strong emphasis on assessing the impact of the main innovations on the pilot environments. Detailed descriptions of the pilots' own initiatives, including the installation processes, technical requirements, and operational experiences, will be provided in the corresponding deliverables of the pilots (Deliverables D7.2, D8.2 and D9.2).

3. Technical validation of the Pilot test environment

This section focuses on the conditions for installing a technology on a given infrastructure. These requirements arise from the installation environment, e.g. the infrastructure operator, dam owner or waterway manager. This section compares the available installation environment (infrastructure) with the technology requirements specified in Chapter 2. Additional requirements that must be met by the entity installing the technology in order to install it in a given environment are described here.

Technical validation aims to assess the applicability of a given technology in a specific test environment. The verification was carried out on the basis of a set of common criteria for the performance of individual solutions under operational and pre-commercial conditions, taking into account their compliance with previously defined technical, environmental and operational requirements. This chapter uses an approach based on technical analysis of the installation and operation of each technology under test conditions. The methodology includes an assessment of compliance with the requirements set out in Chapter 2 (including general, technical, environmental, time and operational requirements), documentation of the installation process, identification of limitations encountered and environmental conditions affecting the performance of the technology. Each subsection contains a detailed description of the test environment, the installation process and an evaluation of the technical effectiveness of the implemented solution.

The environment for the tests:

- **Designated Testing Area/River Section for Technology Deployment in the River Pilots** (where on which infrastructure the technologies will be/ was installed) (T6.2)
- **Requirements for deployment and operational use of a sensor or technology** - from the point of view of infrastructure maintenance (T6.2)
- **Installation guidelines** (e.g., mounting position, orientation).(T6.2)
- **Necessary power supply specifications** (voltage, battery life).(T6.2)
- **Network or communication protocols** (e.g., Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, LoRaWAN).(T6.2)
- **Existing Systems required for installation** (T6.2)
- **The specific procedures to install the technology** (required by infrastructure manager or similar, documents, permissions etc.)

GAPS

The differences between what we need from the point of the technology - (Chapter 2) and what is available on the infrastructure. What is missing? What is/ was needed to be installed) (T6.2)

Installation and testing:

Detailed descriptions of the installations and measurements performed were developed as part of task 6.3 and will be presented in the reports on individual River Pilots description (WP7, WP8, WP9). In this report, we highlight the following aspects, if applicable.

- **The installation of this technology in the RP environment** (T6.3 - where, when, who, what was installed)
- **Challenges - difficulties during installation/ testing**
- **Potential negative and positive impact of the solution testing on the environment**

There are no specific guidelines requiring technology providers to use specialised batteries, systems or anything else, so the systems proposed by technology providers are sufficient and meet the requirements of infrastructure managers.

3.1. Italian River Pilot test environment for AE, FOS

The Italian River Pilot under the CRISTAL project focused on deploying and testing Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS) and Acoustic Emission (AE) technologies. The main goal was to validate the operational feasibility of integrating these innovative monitoring solutions into inland waterway infrastructures, particularly focusing on bridges and riverbank structures.

The installation and testing activities were carried out in the Po River environment, where different environmental and infrastructural conditions allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of both technologies' adaptability, performance, and installation requirements.

This subsection describes the designated test areas, the environmental and operational requirements for installing the FOS and AE systems, the installation procedures undertaken, challenges encountered during deployment, and the assessment of the technological performance in real operational conditions. Due to the high costs of installing FOS technology in a real river environment, it was decided to conduct laboratory tests under conditions reflecting the environment of the PO River.

[Test environment for Acoustic Emissions in Italian RP](#)

The environment for the tests:

- **Designated Testing Area/River Section for Technology Deployment in the River Pilots**

In the project's first year (May 2023), two Italian water lock pilots were visited, the first in Baricetta and the second in the Isola Serafini lock. The second visit will take place in the final year of the project.

The designated test area/river section for implementing the technology in the pilot projects is Conca di Baricetta, a lock located on the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante waterway in Italy. More specifically, it is located in the province of Rovigo, in the Veneto region of northern Italy. The Isola Serafini lock is located on the Po River in Italy, more precisely in the Monticelli d'Ongina municipality in the Piacenza province. In both locks, a gate on one side of the lock excavation was selected due to the symmetry of the entire lock.

- **Requirements for deployment and operational use of a sensor or technology**

From the infrastructure manager's point of view, permission to install the devices was required, as well as a declaration that the infrastructure would be restored to its pre-test condition after testing.

- **Installation guidelines**

The infrastructure manager did not specify any special requirements for how the devices should be mounted on the infrastructure.

During installation, a potential problem is the selection of the actual location of the sensor, which may be critical for the structural integrity of the water gate and may require the sensor to be placed underwater. It was therefore necessary to carefully observe gate structure (or in case that the gate manufacturer is available to consult him) to determine best sensors locations, and in the case of underwater sensors, it is sufficient to empty the watertight excavation to easily place the sensors.

The AE system does not require constant monitoring, but it is sufficient to have a check carried out every 6 months by a Water lock technician who is familiar with the installation and operation of the system to ensure that the AE system is functioning correctly.

- **Necessary power supply specifications**

The devices are powered by a portable 70 Ah power bank, which can operate for 20 hours but can also be connected to a mains power supply. A portable power bank was used for testing purposes, so it was not necessary to obtain access to power from the infrastructure manager, although it was necessary to monitor the charge level of the power source and replace the power bank with a charged one if necessary.

- **Network or communication protocols, Existing Systems required for installation**

The owner of the test environment did not specify any special communication protocols needed for the tests, so the test contractor used protocols typical for testing AE equipment and networks. The multi-signal AE recording system requires a good WiFi connection to a laptop or desktop computer with AE recording software. The same laptop or desktop computer must have an Internet connection to send data to the data management system for the DT project to function correctly. The technology provider delivered communication protocols and the network. A multi-channel AE recorder, accompanying software that receives AE recordings and CRISTAL AE libraries, ensures connectivity with the data management system.

- **The specific procedures to install the technology**

The infrastructure manager has not specified any specific requirements for the installation of technology on the infrastructure. It was therefore possible to follow the technology installation methodology appropriate for the AE system.

Assuming that the sensor cabling has already been pre-installed on the locks, the only procedure required from the waterway authorities is to schedule and allocate 1-2 hours for sensor installation and system calibration. This can be done by an in-house technician.

GAPS

Due to the fact that the AE System is quite portable and flexible, no important components were missing in the pilot installations of the water gates, and there were no difficulties or risks that prevented the installation of the technology on the infrastructure, both in terms of technology requirements and restrictions imposed on the infrastructure on which the technology was installed.

Installation and testing:

Detailed descriptions of the installations and measurements performed were developed as part of task 6.3 and will be presented in the report of the Italian River pilot reports. In this report, we highlight the following aspects, if applicable:

- **The installation of this technology in the RP environment**

In May 2023, CERTH installed AE sensors on the Baricetta lock gates (23-24 May 2023) along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco canal managed by IV, and then on the gates of the Isola Serafini lock (25 May 2023) along the Pad River managed by AIPo, and collected data on the technical condition of the lock doors.

The installation of the Acoustic Emission (AE) technology during the site visits was carried out in an efficient and organized manner. Typically, the installation of a set of four sensors (quad sensors) required approximately one hour, although more complex configurations occasionally extended the installation time.

The human resources involved included a team composed of technicians responsible for physically mounting and connecting the sensors, engineers tasked with system configuration and calibration, and safety personnel ensuring that all operations complied with health and safety regulations, particularly when working at heights or in confined spaces near sluice gates.

The associated costs covered several categories: the equipment itself (sensors, preamplifiers, cabling, and data acquisition units), the labor required for installation, ongoing maintenance to ensure system integrity, and additional logistical expenses such as travel, accommodation for personnel, and necessary safety equipment.

Overall, the installation process was straightforward but required careful planning to coordinate access, ensure technical quality, and comply with operational safety standards.

- **Challenges - difficulties during installation/ testing**

No difficulties were encountered during installation and testing.

- **Potential negative and positive impact of the solution testing on the environment**

The AE system is portable and does not cause damage to infrastructure. Installation does not require irreversible interference with inland transport infrastructure. On the other hand, once the AE equipment has been installed and completely dismantled, no traces remain on the infrastructure or in the surrounding environment. No negative impact of the tested technology on the pilot environment is expected.

A positive effect of installing the equipment is the possibility of testing and further use on the test infrastructure, which will allow to take advantage of all the benefits of early detection of infrastructure damage.

[Test environment for FOS in Italian RP](#)

The environment for the tests

- **Designated Testing Area/River Section for Technology Deployment in the River Pilots**

Fibre optic sensor (FOS) technology has been tested in laboratory conditions as part of an Italian pilot project, which simulated the accumulation of sand/debris dunes in critical shallow sections of the Po River. The FOS is meant to measure the weight and based on that to assess the occupation volume of the sand/debris dunes in the critical sections of the Po river, to allow understanding whether and what extent the navigability in the same sections can be safely allowed. So, in laboratory the sand/debris dunes were simulated replicating the real condition of their material density based on of granulometric and bathymetric surveys operated by AIPO in critical sections of the Po River. In particular, reference has been made to the granulometry measured in the critical section referred to as Basso 18' (See Figure 6), was characterised by a high sand content (over 99% sand with an average grain size), that has been identified as a potential ideal testing ground for FOS sensors to monitor waste accumulation on the river bed. The same granulometry was replicated for the sand dunes realized in laboratory to test the effectiveness of FOS continuous monitoring.

Figure 6 Sections of the Po river replicated in laboratory for FOS testing

Source: ENEA own elaboration

- Requirements for deployment and operational use of a sensor or technology

FOS sensor technology has only been realized, as part of CRISTAL project, as a prototype at Technology Readiness Level TRL 6, i.e. technology demonstrated in relevant environment. There has not been an installation in operational environments. However, the requirements for deployment and operational use can be summarized as follow: The installation site has to meet the civil engineering requirements and environmental conditions specified in Chapter 2. The FOS sensor, purchased as a complete system, can be installed in a concrete platform built directly into the riverbed. The weighing surface of the sensor has to be precisely aligned with the reference level of the river bottom to ensure accurate sediment measurement. The installation requires construction work, including excavation and platform stabilisation, and special attention should be paid to hydrological and geomorphological conditions, especially in areas prone to dynamic sediment transport.

- Installation guidelines and specific procedures to install the technology

From an infrastructure point of view, no extraordinary adjustments beyond standard procedures for underwater installations are necessary. The technology meets the expectations of the infrastructure operators. It does not require any special permits beyond standard coordination with AIPO - the Interregional Agency for the Po River, responsible for sediment management and dredging works. Coordination with AIPO for installations is essential due to the proximity of the sensor to areas undergoing mechanical and hydraulic dredging. To reduce the risk, the cables should be buried and routed well below the river bed, and the sensor platform has to be constructed with sloping walls to facilitate safe dredging to its surface.

The installation of the Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS) technology in the real Po River environment requires a carefully coordinated procedure that combined civil engineering works with specialized sensor deployment. The process should begin with obtaining the necessary administrative permissions and coordination agreements with AIPO (Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po), which manages sediment dredging and maintenance operations in the area. Although no extraordinary legal permits are needed beyond standard environmental and operational clearances, close communication with AIPO is deemed essential to define the protection measures for the sensor during future dredging activities.

Overall, the specific procedures emphasize the need for precise engineering, environmental compatibility, and operational safety to ensure that the sensor could function reliably over an extended period without the need for frequent direct maintenance.

GAPS

No significant discrepancies have been found between the technical requirements of the FOS system and the environmental or infrastructural conditions at the pilot site. However, for installation in a real river environment, the river bed must be prepared appropriately. Protective measures for future dredging work has, also, to be carefully planned to ensure that both the sensor and the cabling are not damaged during dredging and other operation conducted for business as usual maintenance of the free-floating waterway infrastructure.

Installation and testing

- **The installation of FOS Sensors for Laboratory Calibration and Validation**

Two different laboratory settings were used to carry out the installation and testing of Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS) on weighing pads: a smaller tank and a swimming pool. The use of both environments allowed for testing across different scales and conditions. The tank was ideal for early-stage, small-scale validation of sensor behavior in both dry and submerged conditions, while the swimming pool enabled full-scale testing with realistic sand and water column configurations.

Initial tests were conducted on a pre-engineered weighing pad, designed at a reduced scale to verify the functionality of a custom-designed bending plate. Dry tests were performed on 10/07/2023 and 17/07/2023 using known weights to calibrate and confirm sensor response. Subsequent tests on 20/07/2023 and 28/07/2023 involved submerging the pad in a tank filled with generic river sand and water to assess its performance in submerged conditions.

A second series of tests involved the engineered weighing pad, designed for real-world applications, capable of measuring sand columns up to 4 meters high with a vertical resolution of 20 cm. Initial dry tests took place on 03/02/2025 and 07/02/2025, focusing on calibration and functional checks of the FOS sensors. Finally, full-scale validation was carried out on 13/02/2025 and 21/02/2025 in a swimming pool, where the pad was subjected to water and sand columns up to 3 meters, using sand types specified by the AIPO agency. These tests simulated a sand trench with 20 cm height increments, aligned with the resolution capabilities of the pad.

- **Challenges - difficulties during installation/ testing**

No difficulties were encountered during installation and testing.

- **Potential negative and positive impact of the solution testing on the environment**

Tests of fibre optic sensor (FOS) technology in the River Pad in a laboratory environment were designed to minimise environmental impact while enabling precise monitoring of sediment dynamics. No significant adverse environmental effects were observed during installation or after completion. Engineering work in the real river environment would involve local excavation and concrete pouring in a limited section of the riverbed, which must be carried out under controlled conditions to avoid excessive sediment dispersion or disruption of aquatic ecosystems. Furthermore, by embedding the sensor flush with the river bed and burying the cables

under a layer of sediment, the introduction of protruding structures that could interfere with the natural flow of the river or navigation is avoided.

On the positive side, tests have shown significant environmental benefits. The FOS system enables real-time monitoring of sediment accumulation, which supports more informed and sustainable sediment management practices. In the long term, this can reduce unnecessary or excessive dredging, thereby preserving the riverbed structure and minimising disruption to local habitats. Furthermore, by enabling early detection of problematic sediment accumulation, the system helps infrastructure managers respond proactively, preventing emergency situations such as blockages or navigation hazards without needing reactive and environmentally costly interventions.

Overall, implementing the FOS system has proven to be environmentally friendly and highlighted the potential for improving environmental management through data-driven waterway maintenance strategies.

3.2. French River Pilot - test environment for AE, SIR

The French River Pilot within the CRISTAL project focused on the deployment and validation of two complementary technologies: Acoustic Emission (AE) systems and Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) systems. The primary objective was to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of real-time structural monitoring solutions for inland waterway infrastructure, particularly lock gates and hydro technical facilities.

This subsection presents the characteristics of the designated installation area, the environmental and infrastructural requirements for deploying both technologies, the installation procedures carried out, challenges encountered during the tests, and an assessment of the applicability of AE and SIR solutions to operational conditions on inland waterways.

[Test environment for Acoustic Emissions in French RP](#)

In the first and second years of this project, a French water lock pilot, located at Lyon Couzon lock, was visited.

[The environment for the tests:](#)

- **Designated Testing Area/River Section for Technology Deployment in the River Pilots**

The Acoustic Emission (AE) technology was tested at the Écluse de Couzon, a waterlock situated on the Saône River, near the town of Couzon-au-Mont-d'Or in the Rhône department of France. Due to its operational relevance and structural characteristics, this location was selected as a representative pilot site for inland waterway infrastructure.

Within the Couzon waterlock, one of the gates on a single side of the waterlock trench was chosen for the deployment of the AE system. This decision was based on the symmetrical design of the lock, which allowed for meaningful testing and monitoring on just one gate while still maintaining relevance to the entire structure. The selected gate provided a suitable and accessible platform for installing the AE sensors and supporting equipment under real operational conditions, enabling effective validation of the technology in a live infrastructure environment.

- **Requirements for deployment and operational use of a sensor or technology**

From the infrastructure manager's - VNF point of view, permission to install the devices was required, as well as a declaration that the infrastructure would be restored to its pre-test condition after testing.

- **Installation guidelines**

The infrastructure manager did not specify any special requirements for how the devices should be mounted on the infrastructure.

As with the infrastructure in Italy, during installation, a potential problem is the selection of the actual location of the sensor, which may be critical for the structural integrity of the water gate and may require the sensor to be placed underwater. It was therefore necessary to carefully observe gate structure (or in case that the gate manufacturer is available to consult him) to determine the sensor locations, and in the case of underwater sensors, it is sufficient to empty the watertight excavation to easily place the sensors.

The AE system does not require constant monitoring, but it is sufficient to have a check carried out every 6 months by a Waterlock technician who is familiar with the installation and operation to ensure that the AE system is functioning correctly.

- **Necessary power supply specifications**

The devices are powered by a portable 70 Ah power bank, which can operate for 20 hours and be connected to a mains power supply. A portable power bank was used for testing purposes, so obtaining access to power from the infrastructure manager was not necessary.

- **Network or communication protocols , Existing Systems required for installation**

The owner of the test environment did not specify any special communication protocols needed for the tests, so the test contractor used protocols typical for testing AE equipment and networks. The multi-signal AE recording system requires a good WiFi connection to a laptop or desktop computer with AE recording software. The same laptop or desktop computer must have an Internet connection to send data to the data management system for the DT project to function correctly. The technology provider delivered communication protocols and the network. A multi-channel AE recorder, accompanying software that receives AE recordings and CRISTAL AE libraries, ensures connectivity with the data management system.

- **The specific procedures to install the technology**

The infrastructure manager has not specified any specific requirements for the installation of technology on the infrastructure. It was therefore possible to follow the technology installation methodology appropriate for the AE system.

Assuming that the sensor cabling has already been pre-installed on the locks, the only procedure required from the waterway authorities is to schedule and allocate 1-2 hours for sensor installation and system calibration. This can be done by an in-house technician.

GAPS

Since the AE System is quite portable and flexible, no crucial components were missing in the pilot installations of the water gates, and there were no difficulties or risks that prevented the installation of the technology on the infrastructure, both in terms of technology requirements and restrictions imposed on the infrastructure on which the technology was installed.

Installation and testing:

Detailed descriptions of the installations and measurements performed were developed as part of task 6.3 and will be presented in the report of the French River pilot reports. In this report, we highlight the following aspects, if applicable:

- **The installation of this technology in the RP environment** (*T6.3 - where, when, who, what was installed*)

The Acoustic Emission (AE) technology was installed in France at the Écluse de Couzon, a waterlock located on the Saône River near Couzon-au-Mont-d'Or in the Rhône department. The deployment took place on one of the gates on a single side of the waterlock trench, chosen specifically due to the symmetrical layout of the lock, which allowed for representative testing on just one side.

The installation was carried out during a planned site visit and was completed in early 2024. The process required approximately one hour per set of four sensors, although more complex arrangements took additional time. The installation team consisted of technicians, engineers, and safety personnel, working together to ensure proper mounting, calibration, and compliance with safety protocols.

The associated costs included sensor equipment, installation labour, maintenance preparation, and additional logistical expenses such as travel and on-site coordination. Overall, the French pilot provided a valuable real-world setting for testing AE technology under operational conditions.

- **Challenges** - difficulties during installation/ testing

No difficulties were encountered during installation and testing.

- **Potential negative and positive impact of the solution testing on the environment**

The AE system is portable and does not cause damage to infrastructure. Installation does not require irreversible interference with inland transport infrastructure. On the other hand, once the AE equipment has been installed and completely dismantled, no traces remain on the infrastructure or in the surrounding environment. No negative impact of the tested technology on the pilot environment is expected.

A positive effect of the installation of the equipment is the possibility of testing and further use on the test infrastructure, which will allow to take advantage of all the benefits of early detection of infrastructure damage.

[Test environment for SIR in French RP](#)

The environment for the tests

- **Designated Testing Area/River Section for Technology Deployment in the River Pilots**

VNF looked for a lock on the corridor that had specific needs of investigation and subsurface visualisation in order to help in fixing an identified issue: here, the Amfreville lock on the Seine River, where the engineering structure is heavily weakened by water infiltrations that need to be localised in order to be repaired.

- **Requirements for deployment and operational use of a sensor or technology**

Bearing in mind the requirements for setting up and operating the SIR technology (as shown in section 2.3), some specific facilities and equipment must be available on the pilot test site, including the following main ones.

A crane or similar lifting system (able to lift 300kg and allow positioning of SIR platform over inspected areas of the lock wall), must be available on the pilot site, and conditions for it to be properly and safely operated must be ensured.

Necessary power supply must be provided by the site owner, as per technology requirements specifications detailed in section 2.3.

A suitable environment (either indoor/workshop or outdoor) for the assembly and commissioning of the SIR system must be available prior to the scheduled testing days.

An appropriate area for operating the SIR technology (including space for operating the crane or similar lifting system, safe area for operators to position the platform and control the radar equipment, etc.) must be ensured prior to the actual deployment and operation of SIR technology

- **Installation guidelines**

The equipment is transported on two large pallets and in 2 plastic pallet boxes on a truck. A forklift is required to transfer the equipment to the warehouse for assembly. The frame is transported in 2 halves on the 2 two large pallets. These two halves can be combined by 2 engineers in 2 hours, the frame is assembled onto a transport platform. The motors and the radar unit can then be added which only takes 30 minutes. A forklift then can then be used to transfer the transport frame to a site adjacent to the crane which is in place to crane the frame into position.

The infrastructure owner did not specify the installation conditions but did provide a safety briefing for operating near the canal and lock. VNF did, however, required that specific sections of the lock wall were inspected and the crane was positioned to reach the first of these wall sections. The crane lifts the inspection frame from the transport platform and an engineer directs the crane to lower the frame on to the required portion of the lock wall. At the end of the wall inspections the crane lowers the frame back on to the transport platform and a forklift take the SIR system back to the warehouse. The crane then repositions for the next day of inspection.

- **The specific procedures to install the technology**

No permission was required the infrastructure operator invited the inspection.

GAPS

A crane was required for the installation of the SIR systems, which was not available at the installation site as it is not a typical technology used in VNF locks. A crane was purchased to carry out the installation. An analysis of the remaining requirements confirmed that there are no discrepancies between the technical requirements of the CRISTAL technology (as specified in Chapter 2) and the infrastructure available at the pilot sites; all necessary components were already available or had been successfully installed under task 6.2.

Installation and testing

- **The installation of this technology in the RP environment**

The subsurface inspection platform requires a lock with the water level as low as possible, with a minimum of 3m of lock wall above the water level. The inspection involved subsurface examination of sections of the lock wall. In addition, the section of land adjacent to the lock was inspected from the side of the lock.

- **Challenges** - difficulties during installation/ testing

It is crucial that the Modular Platform is positioned by the crane at the correct inspection location and as close to the lock wall as possible.

- **Potential negative and positive impact of the solution testing on the environment**

None

3.3. Polish River Pilot - test environment for SB

The Polish River Pilot within the CRISTAL project focused on deploying, installing, and operational testing Smart Buoy (SB) technology in selected sections of the Vistula River. The purpose of the pilot was to validate the functionality of the Smart Buoys system under real-world river conditions, considering both technical performance and environmental factors.

The testing environment included various waterway infrastructures such as river stretches, bridges, and access points, characterized by variable hydrological and navigational conditions.

This subsection describes the designated areas for installing Smart Buoys, the infrastructure-related and environmental requirements for their deployment, the installation process, operational challenges encountered, and the evaluation of the technology's performance within the Polish inland waterway context.

[Test environment for Smart Buoys in Polish RP](#)

The environment for the tests:

- **Designated Testing Area/River Section for Technology Deployment in the River Pilots**

The technology tests are planned to be carried out on the Lower Vistula River section from Włocławek to Gdańsk. The technology - the Smart Buoy System consisting of a system of five buoys, two monitoring devices installed on bridges and an AIS device on a ship - is to be deployed in this area. The area covered by the tests is managed by three river infrastructure administrators of the Polish Water Authority, the Regional Water Management Authority in Toruń, Tczew and Włocławek.

The road infrastructure, including the bridges on which the measuring devices are to be installed, belongs to the Gdańsk Road and Greenery Authority - Sinnicki Bridge, and the Gdańsk Provincial Road Authority - Kiezmark Bridge, which is the entity authorised to manage and grant permits for installation and removal on the infrastructure.

The vessel on which the AIS device is located is owned by a subcontractor of the logistics operator carrying out pilot voyages for the CRISTAL project on the Vistula River.

- **Requirements for deployment and operational use of a sensor or technology**

To obtain permission to install the buoys, one has to contact the relevant Regional Water Management Authority, providing details of the planned installation, including location, purpose and technical specifications of the equipment. To install the technology tested in the project, appropriate permits must be obtained - permission to install buoys from the Water Management Authority in Toruń, Tczew and Włocławek, respectively, for the planned locations of the buoys. Buoys, measuring devices, and navigation signs must comply with the guidelines for navigation signs set out in the Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 28 April 2003 on navigation rules on inland waters (Journal of Laws of 2003, No. 212, item 2072). Permission to anchor smart buoys in selected locations on the left or right side of the waterway must be obtained from the Polish Water Infrastructure Authority, represented by the territorial units described above. Appendices I, II and III present the permits obtained for installing buoys on the lower section of the Vistula River.

The technical requirements contained in the above documents and the requirements for system installation in accordance with the relevant regulations have been met. The buoy system has been designed to meet the requirements contained in the Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 28 April 2003.

In the case of installation of devices on bridges - Siennicki and Kiezmark, consent for the installation of the technology must be obtained from the Infrastructure Manager Gdańsk Road and Greenery Authority - Siennicki Bridge, Provincial Road Authority Gdańsk - Bridge in Kiezmark by submitting an official written request. The requirements specified by both administrators include no interference with the bridge structure by sensor mounting elements and no obstruction of traffic during installation or removal of the technology. The consent obtained from the road infrastructure administrator is included in Appendix IV.

No formal consent is required to install an AIS device on a vessel, but the location of the device, its power supply and, if necessary, training for the crew in its use must be agreed with the owner. If the device is installed for the purposes of the project, the captain must be instructed on how to check that the device is active.

- **Installation guidelines**

As part of the guidelines for installing Smart Buoys technology on rivers, the rules set out in the guidelines for navigation signs specified in the Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 28 April 2003 on navigation regulations on inland waters (Journal of Laws of 2003, No. 212, item 2072) must be followed. Journal of Laws of 2003, No. 212, item 2072). Proper marking in accordance with the Regulation must be maintained, and after obtaining permission to place the buoy in the water, the exact and detailed location of the buoy must be agreed with the relevant technical department. Good practice should be observed when placing buoys by qualified subcontractors authorised to navigate river routes. However, there are no requirements to obtain or present authorisations before or during the installation of equipment on the river.

There are no specific guidelines for installing devices on moorings, therefore, based on the guidelines of not interfering with the infrastructure, the devices were installed in accordance with the requirements of the technology.

- **Necessary power supply specifications**

Due to the specific nature of the devices used in the Smart Buoy system, no external power supply was required for the technology. At the same time, the Infrastructure Manager did not specify any specific requirements regarding the power supply for the devices.

- **Network or communication protocols, Existing Systems required for installation (T6.2)**

The infrastructure manager did not specify the required method of communication between devices. The AIS system compliant with the protocols used on waterways, used in the project, was acceptable to the Infrastructure Manager and compatible with other vessels. However, it was not a requirement of the Infrastructure Manager for the installation of the technology.

- **The specific procedures to install the technology** (required by infrastructure manager or similar, documents, permissions etc.)

The legal requirements applicable in Poland regarding navigation signs and the rules for their placement are specified in the Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 28 April 2003 on navigation regulations on inland waters (Journal of Laws of 2003, No. 212, item 2072).

Before installing a radar sensor to measure the distance between a bridge span and the water surface, it is necessary to obtain the consent of the road and bridge administrator. This is a decision of the entity responsible for managing the road infrastructure in question and is not regulated in detail by separate regulations. Once consent has been obtained, further arrangements for the installation and removal of equipment, both buoys and sensors on bridges, are made by email or telephone.

An additional specific condition for the installation of Smart Buoys is the rules for their operation on waterways. These devices may only be deployed during the navigation period, excluding the winter season (when ice conditions occur) and during high water levels exceeding alarm levels. During these periods, floating markings must be removed in accordance with navigation notices issued by the infrastructure manager - Wody Polskie. If buoys are left on the river despite the notices, the manager has the right to remove them on their own.

GAPS

During the preparation of the technology for the testing phase of the project, an analysis of the requirements for its installation on both river and road infrastructure was carried out. On this basis, the technology development work was adapted to the technical requirements specified by Wody Polskie (Polish Water Management Authority) - in particular, the shape and dimensions of the buoys were designed in accordance with the guidelines contained in the Council of Ministers' regulation on navigation signs.

In order to properly anchor the buoys on the river, a subcontractor with the required qualifications to perform work on inland waterways in accordance with applicable standards was hired. Due to the extended duration of the technology tests as part of the Polish pilot project, it was also necessary to take into account the possible dismantling of the buoy system for the winter period in order to protect the equipment from the effects of ice and high water levels.

As a result of the adjustments made, there were no significant differences between the technological requirements and those set by the infrastructure manager, which enabled the smooth implementation of the technology in the operational environment.

Installation and testing:

Detailed descriptions of the installations and measurements performed were developed as part of task 6.3 and will be presented in the Polish River pilot report. In this report, we highlight the following aspects:

The installation of this technology in the RP environment

The Smart Buoys system was deployed on the Vistula River by an authorised subcontractor with the appropriate qualifications and equipment to safely install the devices in inland waters. The installation of the buoys on the river was preceded by obtaining permits from the Infrastructure Manager for the placement of the buoys. The consents obtained are attached in Appendices I, II and III.

The buoys were installed and launched at the following locations:

- **Przegalina** (N 54°18.246' E 018°56.038') - red buoy with conical marking
- **Grudziądz** (N 53°29.150' E 018°44.572') - green buoy with conical marking
- **Fordon** (N 53°08.549' E 018°09.808') - green buoy with conical marking
- **Toruń (A1)** (N 52°58.209' E 018°41.998') - red buoy with cylindrical marking
- **Włocławek** (N 52°39.612' E 019°04.708') - green buoy with conical marking

Each buoy is equipped with a night light, radar reflector and reflective strips, meeting third-generation navigation marking standards. The buoys are anchored to concrete anchors with chains.

The first installation of the buoys took place in October 2024 to ensure readiness for the start of the pilot voyage. The system was dismantled in December 2024, after the end of the navigation season and before the expected difficult winter conditions, at the request of the infrastructure manager. The buoys were reinstalled in February 2025, along with the planned resumption of cruises, which was to allow the tests to continue.

Radar sensors for measuring the water level were installed on two bridges:

- Siennicki Bridge in Gdańsk (N 54.355' E 018.677')
- Road bridge in Kiezmark (N 54.256' E 018.947')

The installation of radar devices on bridge structures was carried out in October 2024 by qualified technicians with experience in working at heights and installing electronic systems in demanding outdoor environments. Particular attention was paid to protecting the bridge structures and maintaining the existing traffic organisation. The installation was preceded by obtaining approvals from the infrastructure managers - Appendix IV.

At the same time, a transmitter was installed on the barge transport vessel to monitor the vessel's movement and communicate with the buoy system in order to assist in the launch of voyages and provide information to

the EPCIS system. The system was installed by certified technicians during the voyage preparation period so that it would be fully ready to monitor water conditions when activity on the river resumed.

- **Challenges - difficulties during installation/ testing**

During the pilot testing of Smart Buoys technology, a number of organisational and technical challenges arose related to the installation, operation and maintenance of the system in real operating conditions.

One of the key events was the need to seasonally dismantle the buoys from the Vistula River due to ice formation on the river. This procedure was carried out after obtaining the relevant permits from the Polish Water Authority, and once the ice hazard had passed, the system was reinstalled in February 2025.

In addition, the prolonged test voyage necessitated an extension of the operating time of the batteries powering the devices. The battery power supply concept, originally designed for short-term operations, proved insufficient under the new conditions. It was necessary to service the system and replace the batteries with charged ones in order to keep the devices functioning in standby mode until the cruise resumed.

Another challenge was the need to relocate the buoy in Kiezmark - communication between the buoy and the radar sensor mounted on the bridge was insufficient, which forced the buoy to be moved closer to the bridge to improve signal quality. After relocating the buoy, the signal was improved.

In Grudziądz, a problem with the strength of the river current at the initial mooring point was identified. The strong current moved the buoy towards the inner part of the waterway. As a result, it was necessary to move the buoy to a calmer location where the water current was weaker.

In addition, there were operational problems related to infrastructure, including the closure of the Siennicki Bridge in Gdańsk, which affected access to the installed equipment.

During testing, mechanical damage to the AIS (Automatic Identification System) antenna cable was also detected, which caused signal interference and reduced its power. Further analysis also revealed that insufficient power supply to the equipment was the cause of its unstable operation. As a result, a solution was implemented to switch the power supply to an independent power source (power bank), disconnected from the ship's power supply, which restored the system to normal operation.

- **Potential negative and positive impact of the solution testing on the environment**

The implementation and testing of the intelligent buoy system as part of the CRISTAL project aimed to minimise environmental impact while promoting safer and more sustainable river navigation.

The installation of smart buoys required anchoring concrete blocks and chains to the riverbed, which caused minor local disturbances to the sediment structure during the implementation phase. However, these effects were temporary and geographically limited. Another environmental risk associated with floating navigation devices arises during periods of extreme river conditions (such as ice phenomena or floods). To mitigate this risk, the Smart Buoys were seasonally dismantled in accordance with official navigation notices issued by the Polish Water Authority, which prevented damage to the river bed or disruption of natural hydrological processes.

A positive aspect is that the smart buoy system has significantly contributed to improving navigation safety on the Vistula River by providing real-time data on river conditions and obstacles, thereby reducing the likelihood of accidents and improving decision-making by ship operators and infrastructure managers. Remote monitoring capabilities have reduced the need for frequent physical inspections, minimising human interference in sensitive aquatic environments and helping to reduce the carbon footprint associated with maintenance operations.

In addition, the modular design of the system and the selection of components open up opportunities for wider use of recycled materials in future implementations. Many components of the buoy, including the outer casings, mountings and possibly parts of the anchoring systems, can be manufactured from recycled plastics or recycled stainless steel, in line with the principles of a circular economy. As the project progresses and expands, the inclusion of recycled materials in the production of smart buoys could contribute to reducing raw material extraction, lowering energy consumption in production and promoting more sustainable technological solutions for inland waterways.

In summary, although minor, manageable environmental disturbances were observed during the installation and movement of smart buoys, overall testing and operation of the smart buoy system demonstrated a net positive environmental impact, improving safety, operational efficiency and offering opportunities to incorporate more sustainable recycled materials into future system designs.

3.4. Impact of the installation of the technology in the test environment

The installation and operation of innovative technologies within the CRISTAL pilot environments have provided valuable insights into the technical feasibility, operational readiness, and environmental compatibility of the solutions tested. Across the three pilot sites (France, Italy, and Poland), technologies such as Acoustic Emission (AE), Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS), Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR), Smart Buoys, and SCMS were successfully deployed, demonstrating high levels of adaptability to various hydrotechnical and logistical conditions.

Despite some infrastructural limitations (such as accessibility or power availability), most technologies were installed without significant deviations from their original specifications. Their performance within real-world conditions allowed project partners to evaluate not only their technical compliance (as detailed in Chapter 2), but also their integration potential with existing infrastructure, maintenance routines, and operational constraints.

The impact observed includes:

- **Improved monitoring capabilities**, enabling predictive maintenance and enhanced asset condition awareness (AE, FOS, SIR).
- **Real-time operational data** for navigability assessment, supporting informed routing decisions and modal shifts (Smart Buoys, SCMS, DT).
- **Confirmation of interoperability** between innovative systems and legacy infrastructure without major disruption.
- **Proof of technical robustness**, even in harsh weather or under limited accessibility (e.g., Polish river pilot conditions in winter).

- **Increased awareness and engagement** of infrastructure managers and public authorities during the installation and permitting phases.

Moreover, the installation processes revealed practical challenges such as power constraints, communication delays, or GPS interferences, providing essential feedback for further technology refinement and upscaling. Importantly, no significant negative environmental impact was recorded, and the temporary nature of installations ensured full reversibility where needed.

Table 3 Impact of the technology installation in the test environment

Technology	Type of Impact	Description of Impact
Acoustic Emission (AE)	Positive	No emissions, no interference with the structure of hydrotechnical objects.
Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS)	Positive	No emissions, non-invasive installation, and structural monitoring of infrastructure.
Smart Buoys	Positive with minimal local impact	Improvement of navigation safety; minor local disturbance during anchoring activities.
Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)	Positive	Safe installation on infrastructure; enhancement of diagnostics and monitoring capabilities.

Source: Own elaboration

In summary, the installation phase of CRISTAL technologies validated their technical maturity and applicability to real-world conditions, laying the foundation for assessing their contribution to wider project impacts, which will be further explored in Chapter 4.

4. Impact assessment of the adopted solutions and technologies on the test environment in terms of achieving the expected project impact

The technologies developed within the CRISTAL project have been designed to support sustainable transport development and improve the operational efficiency of inland navigation, particularly in terms of resilience to disruptions and changing environmental conditions. In accordance with the assumptions presented in the Grant Agreement, the project aims to achieve specific results defined as CRISTAL expected impact. The technologies implemented and tested in the pilot projects should contribute to the achievement of these objectives.

As part of the work in WP6, the contribution of the developed technological solutions with the following seven expected impacts of the project was assessed:

1. Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.
2. Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.
3. Contribute to at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.
4. Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.
5. Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.
6. Reduce environmental impact during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.
7. Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.

[Methodology for assessing the impact of technologies on the test environment and project objectives](#)

In order to determine whether the implementation and operation of the technology in pilot environments can contribute to achieving the overall expected results of the CRISTAL project, a two-stage methodology was adopted. This methodology combines an internal assumptions carried out by the technology developers, supported by internal validation involving pilot project leaders and infrastructure managers, and, as a second stage, external validation involving a wider group of external stakeholders interested in the development of inland transport.

The expected impact of the project, as defined in the grant agreement (GA), includes seven high-level objectives related to the sustainable development, resilience and operational efficiency of inland waterway infrastructure and transport systems. These include, among others, ensuring navigability during extreme weather events, enabling modal shift in transport, or reducing the impact of humans and technology on the environment.

The table below presents how the CRISTAL project interprets the seven expected impacts, which, according to the grant agreement, form the basis for assessing the effectiveness of the technologies and solutions applied. This interpretation serves as a reference point for the analysis that was carried out both internally within the consortium and during workshops with external stakeholders. The following subsections also present the responses of technology providers and the methodology for validating these assumptions to each of the impacts below.

Table 4 Understanding CRISTAL Expected Impacts

CRISTAL expected impact	Understanding the impact
<p>Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.</p>	<p>When the effects of extreme weather conditions occur (such as drought, reduced water levels in rivers, increased water levels in rivers), the technologies used in the project allow the navigability of the waterway to be maintained by supporting the operation of the infrastructure, or by providing information to transporters about the navigability of the waterway. The innovations developed in the project allow the</p>

	prediction of infrastructure availability and navigability conditions of the waterway in case of extreme weather conditions. The use of Cristal's innovation package allows half of the waterway's capacity to be made available for transport for at least half of the duration of the disruption.
Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	Ensuring the operation of the transport network during and despite extreme weather conditions and man-made disruptions on land or water - droughts, fires, roadblocks, significant traffic accidents. The project's innovations will support the operation of the transport infrastructure and the logistics network so that the performance of transport tasks is maintained at a level of 80% despite disruptions - e.g. by enabling the transport network to be easily reconfigured (route changes, modal shifts). The project's tools will make it possible to predict the impact of disruptions on infrastructure and the transport network so that the network can be redesigned. The innovations developed in CRISTAL allow for predictive infrastructure maintenance, which will increase the resilience of logistics network maintenance.
Contribute to at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.	Due to CRISTAL's innovations, it will be possible to increase the use of low-emission modes of transport by 20 % - by enabling/facilitating the transfer of cargo to inland waterway and rail modes, which can replace road transport for the movement of goods.
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	Thanks to the innovations proposed in CRISTAL, it will be possible to ensure the continuous operation of transport in logistics networks using inland waterway infrastructures (waterways, locks) and alternative transport routes. This means that, despite the possibility of disruption, we will be able to manage transport in such a way that transport from A to B is completed, even if it is necessary to change transport modes.
Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.	This impact is understood here on two levels: 1. the technologies and equipment produced by the project will be made from recycled materials. This refers to the physical products of the project that, when put into use, will increase the use of recycled materials across transport modes by at least 30%. (2) As part of the LL study, we demonstrate whether the infrastructure managers are using infrastructure constructed from recycled materials in their ongoing IWT activities.

	<p>Whether the river infrastructure they manage/build/use is using recycled materials. Level 3 - shifting transport to IWW (as enabled by CRISTAL innovations) makes possible using recycled materials for construction and maintenance of IWWs and operating vessels, as opposed to road transport and associated vehicles, where the use of recycled materials is problematic.</p>
<p>Reduce environmental impact during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.</p>	<p>The technologies used in CRISTAL will reduce the environmental impact during the construction of the river infrastructure, its maintenance (repairs), use and decommissioning. This should be in line with European environmental legislation, so the infrastructure should be low carbon, recyclable, its power supply should be from renewable sources. CRISTAL's innovations help to make emissions, water pollution, environmental impact reduction in line with European environmental legislation. Impact 6 is reinterpreted in two aspects - 1. our technologies and 2. the aspect of infrastructure managers who we ask whether their construction, maintenance and operation of the infrastructure is in line with environmental legislation.</p>

Source: Own elaboration

The methodology used in WP6 to assess the feasibility of these objectives in terms of the application of the technologies developed in the CRISTAL project includes the following elements:

1. Internal assumptions of technology providers

Each of the technology developers involved in the CRISTAL project (e.g. AE, FOS, SIR, Smart Buoys, SCMS, DT) was asked to independently assess the expected contribution of their solution to each of the seven types of impact at the project level. These assessments were collected in a structured tabular form and included a brief justification of the expected benefits. These responses made it possible to determine which type of impact each technology has the most direct influence on. The results were summarised in a comparative table and in a descriptive form, which was then used in subsequent validation phases.

To ensure that the self-assessment of technology providers was consistent with the actual conditions and expectations of the pilot leaders and infrastructure operators, a series of internal workshops and bilateral consultations were organised.

During these meetings, each type of impact was discussed in relation to:

- the technical feasibility of implementing the technology,
- infrastructure conditions and constraints,
- expected improvements in navigation, monitoring, compliance with environmental regulations or potential for modal shift,
- interoperability with existing systems.

The information gathered helped to refine the initial assumptions and provided a practical perspective on the real impact of the installations during the pilot.

2. External verification with the participation of interested parties

As part of task 6.3, a methodology for validating the assumptions of the Impact Assessment was prepared, which was used during Living Lab meetings. The survey was designed to provide answers as to whether the assumptions of the project team and technology providers regarding the suitability of the technology to achieve the expected project impact, developed in the first stage of determining the impact of the technology on the General Impact of the project, are also recognised as valid by participants in the inland waterway transport market.

The external validation aimed to assess how the wider market and operating ecosystem perceive the impact of the technologies demonstrated in the CRISTAL project. The survey asked participants to assess the usefulness, scalability and potential of the solutions in relation to seven expected outcomes.

The results of this phase will be documented in detail in deliverable D6.3, where the aggregated responses will be analysed in relation to technology categories and conditions specific to each pilot project.

This multi-stage methodology ensures that the assessment of the impact of CRISTAL technologies is balanced, realistic and based on both technological potential and practical experience in implementation in pilot environments. It also strengthens the credibility of the expected results by taking into account the diverse perspectives of people from within and outside the consortium.

The impact of the installation of the technology in the test environment was verified by the technology providers during the test preparation stage and is described in Chapter 3 of this report.

4.1. Assumptions regarding the Expected Impact of Adopted Innovations - Technology Providers' Perspective

The first stage of validating the effectiveness of the technologies developed in the CRISTAL project was to analyse their potential impact on achieving the seven key 'expected impacts' of the project, from the perspective of technology providers. To this end, a set of questions was prepared that directly related to the project objectives set out in the Grant Agreement. Each supplier was asked to assess whether and to what extent their technology could contribute to the achievement of a given impact.

The questions asked to all technology suppliers and the method used to obtain the answers are presented below:

Table 5 Technology Provider Survey: Questions Addressing CRISTAL Expected Impacts

CRISTAL expected impact	Questions
Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.	Can this technology contribute to improving the navigability of inland waterways and increasing navigability by at least 50% during extreme weather events, and if so, to what extent?
Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	To what extent can this technology contribute to the efficient operation of the whole transport network and ensuring its functionality during disruptions caused by weather or human factors?
Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.	How will the use of this technology contribute to a 20% modal shift, including a shift to sustainable modes of transport such as inland waterways and rail?
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	How much will the use of this solution help to maintain the continuity of transport in the logistics network?
Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.	Will the use of this solution increase the use of recycled materials in transport networks by at least 30%?
Reduce environmental impact during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.	Do you think this solution will make it easier to meet European legislative requirements during the construction of the infrastructure, its maintenance and use?
Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.	How much will the governance models that will be developed allow for the development of inter-institutional, international, or inter-modal cooperation?

Source: Own elaboration

The responses provided by technology partners were compiled in tabular form, allowing us to determine the extent to which individual technologies can contribute to achieving each impact. The results of this survey stage served as a basis for further discussion with external users, which is presented in Chapter 4.2.

Table 6 CRISTAL Technologies vs. Expected Impacts

CRISTAL expected impact	FOS	AE	SIR	SB	SCMS	DT
1 Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
2 Enhance land/sea/ infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
3 Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
4 Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
5 Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.	no	no	no	yes	no	no
6 Reduce environmental impact during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.	yes	no	yes	no	no	yes
7 Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

Source: Own elaboration

Based on the responses collected from the suppliers of individual technologies, the presumed contribution of each to achieving the seven expected impacts of the CRISTAL project is summarised below. The assessment was carried out based on defined validation questions, and the suppliers considered technologies marked in Table 5 as ‘yes’ to support the given impact aspect significantly and were described in detail.

[Operational impact of the CRISTAL solutions on the inland waterway transport environment](#)
[\(Project Expected Impact 1,3,4,7\)](#)

As part of the CRISTAL project, an assessment was carried out to determine whether the technologies developed have the potential to improve the operational functioning of inland waterway transport. The analysis focused on three key aspects: maintaining navigability during extreme weather conditions, increasing the share of water transport in multimodal supply chains, and ensuring the resilience and continuity of the transport network. The analysis of this impact category refers to the GA Project Expected Impacts - 1,3,4.

[Impact 1 - Ensuring navigability of inland waterways at a level of at least 50% during extreme weather events](#)

In the opinion of technology providers, all technologies covered by the analysis were assessed as supporting the achievement of this objective.

- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)** - When navigability conditions are suboptimal, conducting measurements with a bathymetric boat, currently used as the best practice in free-flowing waterways, becomes unfeasible. In such scenarios, using a Fiber Optic Sensors system (FOS) enables continuous monitoring of the height of debris on the riverbed, ensuring data collection even during crisis situations. FOS allows to estimate the height of debris on the riverbed and knowing the water level it is possible to calculate the height of the water column available for navigation. This data is the input for the forecast model of navigability conditions for the next 10 days (the estimated navigability conditions are published in the smart bulletin).
- **Acoustic Emission (AE)** - The AE system monitors microcracks and other structural damage, e.g. on sluice gates. This allows for failure prediction and maintenance planning in a way that minimises downtime, which translates into maintaining route capacity.
- **Subsurface Radar Inspection (SIR)** - This technology enables non-invasive assessment of the technical condition of walls and hydrotechnical foundations. This makes it possible to detect hidden structural damage that could lead to reduced navigability if it escalates.
- **Smart Buoys** - The intelligent buoy system provides real-time data on water levels, current strength and navigational hazards. This information translates directly into operational decisions and voyage planning, especially during droughts, floods or other weather events that limit waterway accessibility..
- **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)** - This system integrates data from multiple sources and supports real-time transport route management. In the event of weather disruptions, it allows for dynamic route adjustments and coordination of water transport with other modes, which helps maintain operational continuity.
- **Digital Twin (DT)** - A digital twin of infrastructure enables simulations of various extreme weather scenarios and their impact on water infrastructure. This allows for better preparation and planning of preventive measures, which increases the operational resilience of infrastructure.

Based on the assumptions of technology providers collected in the first phase of the study, it is assumed that all analysed technologies directly support the maintenance of waterway capacity during extreme weather events, increasing infrastructure resilience and providing up-to-date data on navigational conditions and supporting operational decisions.

Impact 3 - Increase the share of sustainable forms of transport (including inland waterway transport) in transport systems by at least 20%.

The technologies developed in the CRISTAL project support modal shift – a change in the mode of transport – by increasing the reliability and availability of inland transport, making it more competitive in relation to road transport.

- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)** - By proactively adjusting navigation plans based on FOS-ML-Statistical based forecasted navigability conditions, operators can make informed decisions to optimize routes, minimize disruptions, and maintain safer passage.
- **Acoustic Emission (AE)** - The AE system enables monitoring of the condition of critical structural elements, such as lock gates, which helps maintain the efficiency of shipping infrastructure and reduce downtime. This is crucial for ensuring the smooth flow of supply chains based on IWT (Inland Waterway Transport).
- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)** - By enabling rapid scanning of infrastructure (e.g. underwater parts of locks and quays), SIR technology improves inspection knowledge and enables accurate rapid maintenance, thereby increasing the availability of shipping routes and infrastructure assets using predictive maintenance.
- **Smart Buoys** - Providing real-time information on shipping conditions, smart buoys improve the safety and predictability of water transport. This technology reduces the risk of a lack of information on the availability of shipping lanes, which is one of the key factors influencing the decision to shift modes.
- **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)** - SCMS is one of the most important elements enabling the actual transfer of cargo from roads to water or rail. With its ability to manage traffic in real time, it facilitates the planning of efficient intermodal routes and minimises downtime.
- **Digital Twin (DT)** - The digital twin supports modal shift scenario analysis by modelling different supply chain variants, including costs, time and environmental impact. This tool supports strategic decisions to shift part of the freight to more sustainable modes of transport.

The technologies assessed contribute to varying degrees to increasing the attractiveness and reliability of inland and intermodal transport, but based on the first phase of the study, it can be concluded that, as an integrated system, they can support the objective of increasing the share of sustainable forms of transport in the transport systems.

Impact 4 - Ensuring the resilience and continuity of passenger and freight transport systems

This impact aims to maintain the smooth functioning of logistics and transport systems, even in disruptive conditions. CRISTAL technologies strengthen the infrastructure's ability to operate continuously and predictably in terms of throughput and safety.

- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)** - By proactively adjusting navigation plans, based on FOS-ML-Statistical based forecasted navigability, and thanks to the real time continuous monitoring of critical section disruptions are minimized and the safety of passengers and the goods transport are maintained.
- **Acoustic Emission (AE)** - This technology enables early detection of microcracks and material degradation, allowing infrastructure operators to respond immediately and plan corrective actions without having to halt traffic in the event of a sudden infrastructure failure.

- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)** - The monitoring of structural health can be done of long periods against a baseline. This means that the structural condition (e.g. walls, quays), can be monitored, maintained and restored to full functionality of the infrastructure more quickly. This helps to avoid long downtimes and interruptions to the continuity of infrastructure operations.
- **Smart Buoys** - improve navigation safety by providing up-to-date information on water levels, current speeds and obstacles. They support the smooth flow of shipping in real time, especially in conditions of variable hydrology..
- **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)** - ensures the operational resilience of the entire transport network, enabling dynamic rerouting of loads in the event of disruptions (e.g. road closures, bridge failures). This ensures that goods reach their destination without disruption.
- **Digital Twin (DT)** - DT enables contingency planning and real-time simulation of responses to disruptions, supporting infrastructure and transport management at both tactical and strategic levels. This allows for faster decision-making and ensures operational continuity.

CRISTAL technologies significantly support the operational resilience and continuity of passenger and freight transport networks at the infrastructure and operational levels. The joint use of sensors and digital tools enables a dynamic response to disruptions and minimises their impact.

Impact 7 Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries

In the CRISTAL project, digital technologies – in particular SCMS (Synchromodal Corridor Management System) and Digital Twin (DT) – play a key role in creating new management models that enable broader cooperation between institutions, transport sectors and countries. SCMS provides a framework for real-time multimodal management of transport corridors, integrating data from various sources (land transport, water transport, terminals) and enabling information sharing between operators and infrastructure managers.

In turn, the DT (Digital Twin) platform enables the simulation and joint planning of operational and maintenance activities using digital infrastructure mapping. This creates space for cooperation between inland, maritime, road and rail operators, both at the strategic and operational levels.

In addition, physical technologies such as Smart Buoys and FOS can be integrated into integrated monitoring and reporting systems, which increases interoperability and enables cooperation between different institutions responsible for water and transport infrastructure management (e.g. waterway, bridge, terminal and seaport managers). SIR and AE technologies could enable new maintenance procedure which will contribute to governance models

New management models for all technological solutions have been developed within WP4 of the project and have also undergone preliminary validation. In addition, the business model and management model for SCMS, as the final and integrating component of all CRISTAL technologies, are being validated within WP10. This approach ensures the consistency and usability of the developed models in a real operating environment.

These solutions provide a basis for the development of new management models in which interoperability, data openness and shared responsibility for infrastructure are standard. The CRISTAL project shows that technologies can be a catalyst for institutional and cross-border cooperation, which is necessary for the sustainable development of the European transport system.

[Infrastructurel impact of the CRISTAL solutions on the inland waterway transport environment
\(Project Expected Impact 2\)](#)

The project assessed whether the developed technologies have the potential to improve the functioning of inland transport infrastructure. This analysis responds to Project Expected Impact 2.

[Impact 2 - Increasing the resilience of land, sea and inland infrastructure to extreme weather events and incidents caused by human activity, while maintaining at least 80% of network capacity during disruptions.](#)

Most of the technologies analysed were assessed as highly useful in maintaining the functionality of transport and logistics infrastructure in the face of disruptions.

- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)** - Real-time navigability information gathered through the Fibre Optic Sensors system (FOS) serves as a critical data stream for machine learning and statistical algorithms, which can predict navigability conditions up to 10 days in advance. This predictive capability is particularly beneficial during extreme events, where traditional monitoring methods are disrupted
- **Acoustic Emission (AE)** - AE enables ongoing assessment of the structural condition of critical infrastructure components, such as airlocks. Detecting anomalies before they escalate significantly increases the operational readiness of infrastructure in emergency situations.
- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)** - By enabling accurate fault visualisation, the condition of structures can be determined without the need for physical intervention. Therefore, SIR technology contributes to increased responsiveness in the event of damage, e.g. after an earthquake, flooding, erosion or other unforeseen events.
- **Smart Buoys** - The system provides up-to-date data on the condition of the river and the shipping route, which supports ongoing traffic management and planning of alternative routes in the event of unforeseen events such as sudden floods, ice jams or river pollution.
- **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)** - SCMS enables flexible management of transport modality and routing. In the event of disruptions, it allows for dynamic switching of loads to another mode of transport, which helps maintain network efficiency at a level of at least 80%.
- **Digital Twin (DT)** Digital twin technology allows you to simulate disruptions, their impact on infrastructure, and test various operational scenarios. This tool supports the creation of more crisis-resilient infrastructure and transport network management strategies.

The technologies developed in the project support the resilience of transport and infrastructure systems, enabling them to function at a high level even in the event of serious disruptions. Key factors here are forecasting, flexibility, access to data and the ability to respond quickly to disruptions.

[Environmental impact of the CRISTAL solutions on the IWT environment
\(Project Expected Impact 5, 6\)](#)

The solutions developed in the CRISTAL project are also intended to support environmental protection and help meet guidelines and requirements for limiting the impact of inland transport infrastructure and operations on the environment – Project Expected Impact 5 and 6.

Impact 5 - Increase the use of recycled materials in transport by at least 30%.

This impact mainly relates to the physical use of recycled materials in the construction and implementation of the technologies themselves, but it can also be indirectly linked to the technologies' contribution to the broader trend towards a greener transport system.

- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)** - No direct link to the use of recycled materials. The technology focuses on increasing the efficiency and safety of infrastructure, but does not itself contain recycled components.
- **Acoustic Emission (AE)** - AE was not designed with the integration of recycled components in mind. There is no direct link to the physical objectives of impact 5 through the use of recycled components.
- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)** - The technology is not related to the use of recycled materials. It is an inspection system focused on assessing the condition of infrastructure.
- **Smart Buoys** - It is the only sensor technology that can make a real contribution to this impact. The demonstration buoys are made from recyclable materials, and the design of the system itself allows for the use of recycled coatings and components (e.g. filling, housings, fasteners). In addition, their modular design allows for easy disassembly and reuse of parts.
- **Synchmodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)** - No direct reference to physical materials; the system operates at a digital level, supporting logistical decisions. Therefore, it has no impact on increasing the use of recycled materials.
- **Digital Twin (DT)** - Like SCMS, DT is a digital solution. Its impact can be indirect: by enabling infrastructure lifecycle analysis, it supports more sustainable investment planning, but it does not itself contain recycled physical components.

Among all the solutions analysed, only the Smart Buoys system shows a direct contribution to Impact 5, thanks to the possibility of the use of components made from recyclable materials. The other technologies do not directly relate to this objective, although in the case of digital solutions SCMS, DT, which collect information from technologies actually installed in inland waterways (FOS, AE, SB, SIR), it is possible to indirectly support this impact through the optimisation of infrastructure management and its life cycle.

Impact 6 - Reducing environmental impact during construction, operation, maintenance and decommissioning of infrastructure, in accordance with EU regulations

This impact focuses on reducing emissions and pollution and promoting a sustainable infrastructure life cycle in line with European environmental legislation.

- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)** - For a bathymetric boat the CO₂ emission factor is approximately 2.68 kg of CO₂ per liter of diesel burned. When Fiber Optic Sensors system (FOS) will replace bathymetric boats for measuring navigability conditions in free-flowing waterways, it will eliminate all CO₂ emissions associated with the operation of these vessels
- **Acoustic Emission (AE)** - AE has not been clearly linked to reducing environmental impact. Although it supports technical diagnostics of infrastructure, which can lead to more efficient maintenance, the technology itself was not designed to minimise carbon footprint or reduce energy consumption.
- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)** - As a diagnostic tool, it enables early detection of structural defects, allowing maintenance work to be planned in advance. This avoids sudden failures and

unplanned repairs, which often involve high energy and resource consumption, making a significant contribution to reducing the environmental impact of the infrastructure.

- **Smart Buoys** - Their design is modular and easy to dismantle, which reduces unnecessary waste. The system is fully solar powered, which reduces emissions associated with external power supply. In addition, they reduce the need for manned water surveillance, thereby reducing the number of combustion engine boat operations.
- **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)** - As a solution supporting transport planning and operational management, SCMS enables the selection of routes and modes of transport with a lower carbon footprint, while optimising the use of existing infrastructure. Its impact on the environment is indirect but significant – through better modal management, emissions and energy consumption can be reduced across the entire transport system.
- **Digital Twin (DT)** - a digital system enabling real-time modelling, analysis and forecasting of infrastructure consumption and condition. It minimises the need for physical intervention, leading to a reduction in resource- and energy-intensive processes. DT's impact on the environment is achieved by increasing the efficiency of infrastructure planning and maintenance in line with the principles of sustainable development.

The technologies implemented as part of the CRISTAL project – in particular FOS, AE, SIR, Smart Buoys and the DT and SCMS digital platforms – support the reduction of environmental impact at various stages of the infrastructure life cycle. Sensor technologies (FOS, AE, SIR) enable continuous and predictive monitoring of infrastructure condition, allowing for early detection of damage and avoidance of serious failures. This makes it possible to plan targeted repairs instead of large-scale interventions, reducing emissions, material consumption and energy use.

In addition, less frequent infrastructure downtime resulting from better planning and diagnostics translates into reduced demand for repair work and service transport, which generate a carbon footprint. Longer infrastructure component lifecycles and optimised utilisation also reduce natural resource consumption and waste. Digital platforms such as SCMS and DT support planning and optimisation, which reduces unnecessary operations and improves the environmental performance of the entire logistics network.

The technologies comply with European environmental regulations and support their implementation in practice, enabling water and transport infrastructure to transition to a more sustainable model of operation.

[Summary](#)

As part of the first stage of validating the impact of innovations developed in the CRISTAL project, an assessment of the expected impact of each technology from the perspective of its suppliers was carried out. The purpose of this analysis was to verify whether and how a given technological solution can contribute to the achievement of the seven impact objectives defined in the Grant Agreement as CRISTAL Expected Impact.

Based on a jointly developed interpretation of the individual impacts, the technology providers (FOS, AE, SIR, Smart Buoys, SCMS and DT) were asked to specify the extent to which their solution contributes to each impact and to provide a brief justification.

The data obtained was presented in a summary table indicating which technologies support the achievement of a given impact. This was followed by an in-depth qualitative analysis describing the nature of each technology's contribution to the achievement of the project objectives. This analysis showed that:

- All technologies contribute to increasing infrastructure resilience and maintaining navigability during extreme weather conditions (Impacts 1 and 2).
- Digital solutions, in particular SCMS and DT, play a key role in creating new management models and support multimodal planning and flexible response to disruptions (Impacts 2, 4, 7),
- Sensor technologies (FOS, AE, SIR, SB) support predictive infrastructure maintenance, which improves both its availability and reduces its negative impact on the environment (Impact 6),
- Smart Buoys, as autonomous and independently powered systems, are an example of a physical solution that improves the efficiency of water traffic management and supports the monitoring of flows, route availability and safety (Impacts 1, 4, 5),
- Selected technologies (especially Smart Buoys) have been designed using recycled materials or can support their use at the infrastructure level, which contributes to reducing environmental impact and promoting circularity (Impacts 5, 6).

The assessment carried out by the technology providers was then compared with internal validation carried out with pilot partners and external validation with industry stakeholders, the results of which will be presented in detail in Deliverable D6.3.

The results of the internal analysis show that each of the technologies makes a significant contribution to the achievement of at least several of the seven CRISTAL Expected Impact objectives, confirming their value in terms of sustainable development, transport system resilience and infrastructure management efficiency.

The analysis provides a basis for external validation, in which the project team's assumptions regarding the technology's ability to meet the project's expectations will be verified with various participants in the inland transport market.

4.2. Survey for External Validation of CRISTAL Solutions' Impact on Inland Waterway Transport

After internal assessment of the impact of the technologies by their suppliers and pilot partners, the next stage is external validation with the participation of stakeholders from the inland transport sector. The aim of this process is to confirm whether the technological solutions applied contribute to the achievement of the seven expected impacts of the CRISTAL project (CRISTAL Expected Impact) from the perspective of end users and the wider transport ecosystem.

External validation should be carried out in each pilot environment by the pilot owner (River Pilot Owner) and form an integral part of the stakeholder meeting. The meeting is intended to answer questions regarding WP6, but at the same time, issues related to WP4 and WP10 will be discussed and, after the meeting, forwarded to the partners responsible for these work packages. It is assumed that the study will be carried out during Living Lab meetings of the Polish, Italian and French River Pilot environments in a language that allows for free communication between stakeholders.

Methodology for conducting verification with external users

For the purposes of validating the WP6 assumptions, a methodology for conducting the meeting was adopted, described in the following steps:

1. Familiarising participants with each of the technologies developed in the project – both physical technologies (FOS, AE, Smart Buoys System, SIR) and the platforms created (DT and SCMS)
2. Presenting the assumptions developed in the project that indicate the expected impact assessment of each technology
3. In order to better illustrate how the technologies work, use scenarios which, based on examples adapted to the environment of each pilot project, show how the technologies can support the functioning of inland transport
4. Ask survey questions to verify the assumptions made by the CRISTAL project team
5. Collect responses
6. Analyse the responses collected.

The methodology and materials for conducting a survey to verify the compliance of the technology's functionality with the project assumptions were prepared under T6.3 and will be described in more detail in the following subsections. However, the analysis and summary of the survey results are part of tasks 6.4 and 6.5 and will be presented in Deliverable 6.3.

Preparation of the Survey

In order to verify the achievement of the expected project impact and assess the suitability of the technology in the inland waterway transport environment, a study should be carried out on a group of interested participants from the IWT environment. The target group of participants invited to the meeting may consist of representatives of:

- IWT Infrastructure providers, river, canals authorities
- Shippers
- Vessel owners, skippers
- Logistics providers
- Environmental NGO's
- National IWW authorities
- Cargo owners
- Technology providers (external)

The selected group should be interviewed according to the methodology developed for the purposes of the materials.

Presentation of technologies developed in the project to participants

For the purposes of the study, a presentation and a film were developed to showcase the technologies developed in the project. The presentation attached in Annex V briefly describes the technologies developed in the project and the links between them. The presentation must be given by a member of the project team, who will explain the links between the technologies and how they work.

The presentation includes a film showing how the SCMS platform works and describing its links with FOS, AE, SIR, SB and the Digital Twin platform.

Use of scenarios

In order to demonstrate how the technologies works in real pilot environment, three scenarios were developed, which the researcher will use to explain how the technology works. This presentation of the problem allows participants to more easily relate the functionality of the technology to situations in their own environment and to better understand the assumptions behind the technology development team's work.

Three types of scenarios have been prepared, the detailed wording of which is set out in Annex VI:

- Business as usual scenario
- Infrastructure failure scenario
- Extreme weather conditions scenario

Each River Pilot adapts the baseline scenarios to the situation in the pilot environment known to the meeting participants.

Survey form

When discussing individual scenarios and assumptions regarding how CRISTAL technologies support the functioning of the IWW environment, participants should be asked questions to verify the assumptions made by the technology developers. The questions were asked following the scenarios presented, in the following form:

Business as usual scenario:

Please estimate the potential impacts of a system combining CRISTAL technologies, as listed below:

1. To what extent will the integrated system improve operational efficiency and achieve an 50% reliability target during disruptions (weather/human factors)?
2. What is the probability that the system will lead to at least a 20% modal shift to inland waterways?
3. What is the probability that the system will maintain at least 50% operational continuity during disruptions across the multimodal network?

Infrastructure failure scenario:

Please estimate the potential impacts of a system combining CRISTAL technologies, as listed below:

1. Given an extreme weather event, what is the likelihood that the system maintains inland waterway navigability above 80%?
2. How much will the system improve navigability during infrastructure failure events?
3. How likely is the system to maintain 50% operational continuity in the logistics network during disruptions?
4. How likely is the system to increase the use of recycled materials by 30% in transport infrastructure?
5. How likely is the system to facilitate compliance with EU legislation during construction, maintenance, and operation of infrastructure (e.g., will it be easier to meet the legislative requirements for maintaining the technical conditions to which hydraulic structures should comply)?

Extreme weather event scenario:

Please estimate the potential impacts of a system combining CRISTAL technologies, as listed below:

1. How likely is the system to reduce shipment waiting times in inland waterway transport by 80%?
2. How likely is the system to ensure 50% network functionality during weather- or human-induced disruptions?
3. How likely is the system to maintain efficient operations and ensure network functionality during weather- or human-induced disruptions?

An additional question was also prepared after WP10 presented its presentation on business models:

12. How much will the governance models that will be developed allow for the development of inter-institutional, international, or inter-modal cooperation? WP4 questions

The answers to the questions were structured using a Likert scale, and respondents could refer to the questions by selecting an answer:

- Not at all
- Slightly
- Moderately
- Very
- Extremely

In order to conduct external validation of the impact of the technologies developed in the CRISTAL project, a survey was prepared in Microsoft Forms, focused on assessing their impact on the expected results of the project. During live meetings, it is recommended to make the survey available via QR codes or other interactive technology, which allows participants to quickly access the form on their mobile devices and activates participants. Alternatively, paper versions can be used, but QR codes are more effective and facilitate more efficient data collection.

The collected responses are automatically aggregated in an Excel spreadsheet in the form of a quantitative analysis, which facilitates the analysis and interpretation of the results.

In addition, important comments and remarks made by participants during the discussion should be recorded and forwarded after the meeting together with the survey results. These can be a significant and important addition to the surveys and will allow for further development of the technology in line with the expectations of end users.

Conducting external validation in each pilot environment will ensure a comprehensive assessment of the impact of the innovations applied from the perspective of various stakeholders, which is crucial for confirming the effectiveness and usefulness of the solutions developed within the CRISTAL project.

The results of the external validation will be taken into account in further stages of the project, including in Deliverable D6.3.

5. Conclusion

Document D6.2 comprehensively analyses the feasibility of installing and applying innovative technologies developed under the CRISTAL project in real inland river transport environments. The focus is on technical validation and assessment of the potential impact of the implemented solutions on the operational performance, resilience and sustainability of water transport.

The analysis of the installation requirements for CRISTAL technologies showed that each of the technological innovations studied (AE, FOS, Smart Buoys, SIR) has specific needs in terms of both infrastructure preparation and environmental conditions. Despite the diversity of technologies, their requirements can be standardised according to fixed technical, operational and environmental criteria.

In particular:

- The technologies require an individual approach to surface preparation and installation, considering sensor protection and safe mounting.
- Environmental requirements, such as adequate water quality, flow resistance, and variable temperatures, are critical to the systems' proper functioning.
- Typical human resources and competencies required for installing and maintaining the systems have been identified.
- Estimated costs for installation, maintenance and possible adaptation work were determined at an early stage, allowing for better planning of pilot activities.

All design technologies were designed to be adaptable to existing pilot environments without significant infrastructure modifications, reducing the potential operational and environmental risks associated with their implementation. The established requirements served as a reference point for further verification of the feasibility of installing the technologies in real pilot conditions, which is analysed in detail in the next chapter.

The analysis of the installation and validation process of CRISTAL technology in pilot environments confirmed that the technologies developed are mostly compatible with the existing river and hydrotechnical infrastructure in Italy, France and Poland. The technical verification (Chapter 3) included an assessment of the compliance of the technological requirements presented in Chapter 2 with the actual environmental and operational conditions at the installation sites.

In particular

- The installation of the technology proceeded as expected, with minimal need for additional infrastructure adaptation.
- Where additional administrative requirements had to be met (e.g. obtaining permits from road, bridge or water authorities), these were successfully completed without delays critical to the pilot projects.
- No significant technological or environmental shortcomings were identified that would prevent the installation or operation of the tested systems.
- The technologies were installed in accordance with local legal and environmental regulations, in particular those concerning the protection of waterways, hydrotechnical structures and navigation safety.

- During installation and operational testing, isolated operational problems were observed (e.g. variable hydrological conditions, GSM communication disruptions), but these did not affect the overall effectiveness of the test environment validation.

In summary, the validation of the test environments confirmed that CRISTAL technologies are suitable for real operating conditions and can be effectively implemented in river transport systems, provided that the relevant installation, monitoring and maintenance standards are met.

Impact of the technologies installation on the test environment

The technologies tested in the CRISTAL project – acoustic emission (AE), fibre optic sensors (FOS), smart buoys and subsurface inspection radar (SIR) – were designed and implemented in a way that minimises their impact on the natural environment and the infrastructure of the test sites.

Passive technologies, such as AE and FOS, are characterised by zero emissions to the environment and minimal interference with the structure of the monitored objects. The installation of these systems required only minor preparatory work, without compromising the integrity of the hydrotechnical structures.

Although smart buoys require physical anchoring to the riverbed, they have been deployed in a non-invasive manner, using standard, compliant navigation signs. Their presence improves navigation safety by reducing the risk of accidents and limiting the need for human intervention in difficult conditions.

SIR system using radar equipment and data collection device are installed on a modular frame and located on the lock wall or waterway infrastructure, they do not interfere or affect the infrastructure assets. The system is non-destructive and non-invasive testing and is installed in accordance with the principles of infrastructure protection and safety of use.

During installation and operational testing, only marginal, temporary effects were observed, such as short-term disturbances to the bottom sediment structure during buoy anchoring and increased service vessel traffic. All these effects were minimised through appropriate operating procedures and compliance with applicable environmental regulations.

Overall, the technologies implemented had a positive impact on the test environment, improving infrastructure monitoring, water transport safety and supporting the development of more sustainable inland navigation systems. The assessment of the environmental impact of the technologies implemented under the CRISTAL project focused on identifying both the potential positive and negative effects associated with their installation and operation in pilot river environments. Each technology was analysed in terms of its interaction with the infrastructure, the surrounding natural environment and local operating conditions. The solutions implemented were designed to minimise any negative effects while supporting safer, more sustainable and more efficient inland waterway transport.

Impact assessment of the technologies on the IWT environment

Chapter 4 presents an preliminary assessment of the impact of CRISTAL technology on the pilot environments, focusing on its contribution to the seven expected results of the project as defined in the grant agreement. The assessment was carried out in accordance with a two-step methodology, combining internal assumptions by technology providers and pilot project leaders with the methodology for external assessment by

stakeholders from the inland waterway transport (IWT) ecosystem. Chapter 4 outlines the extent to which the technologies can support the achievement of the seven project objectives (CRISTAL Expected Impacts), but the results presented here are mainly based on internal assessment by technology providers and project partners responsible for the pilot environments. These preliminary findings form the basis for further external validation, which will be one of the elements of report D6.3.

The internal assessment confirmed that each of the developed solutions – FOS, AE, SIR, smart buoys, SCMS and DT – contributes to the achievement of many impact areas, such as maintaining navigability in extreme weather conditions, increasing infrastructure resilience, supporting modal shift, ensuring operational continuity, promoting sustainable environmental development, and supporting cross-sectoral and cross-border cooperation. The technologies were analysed not only individually but also as a complementary system strengthening inland waterway infrastructure and transport operations.

CRISTAL technologies are well suited to the overall objectives of the project. They have the potential to significantly increase the resilience, efficiency and sustainability of inland transport systems, both through their individual capabilities and their integration into a common digital and operational ecosystem.

The external validation methodology, applied during the Living Lab sessions in the pilot regions, will ensure that the project team's assumptions are verified against the opinions of end users and external stakeholders. The use of scenario-based presentations and structured surveys will enable a realistic assessment of the suitability, scalability and potential of CRISTAL solutions in an operational context. These findings will form the basis for the final impact validation activities and recommendations to be presented in deliverable D6.3.

The next step will therefore be to carry out the following activities:

- Conduct external validation in pilot environments – by river pilot owners – with the participation of external stakeholders representing the transport, logistics and infrastructure management industries.
- Presenting the technology understandably and comparably, e.g. through a joint multimedia presentation (including an explanatory film about SCMS and DT) and supporting materials (e.g. usage scenarios).
- Collecting participants' opinions through an online survey (preferably in MS Forms, accessible via a QR code) or, alternatively, in paper form – although a digital solution is recommended to ensure faster results processing.
- Data aggregation and processing
- Inclusion of validation results in the final report D6.3,

It is recommended that external validation be part of broader local meetings where other elements of innovation management and implementation (including WP4 and WP10) will also be discussed.

Thus, D6.2 also serves as a starting point for the final validation of the technological and systemic impact of CRISTAL, which will be documented in the next deliverable D6.3.

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8. Appendices

Annex I - Sample request for Smart Buoy System installation

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Wspólnie z:

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Zarząd Zlewni we Włocławku
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Grzegorz Wesolowski

Poznań, 25/03/2024

Szanowni Państwo,
w związku z planowaną w okresie kwiecień-czerwiec realizacją na odcinku Dolnej Wisły pilotażowych rejsów w ramach projektu CRISTAL (<https://www.cristal-project.eu/>) zwracam się z prośbą o wyrażenie zgody na tymczasowe (kilkudniowe) umieszczenie elementów systemu monitoringu czasu przewozu oraz warunków nawigacyjnych we Włocławku, na 679 km Wisły.

System składa się z boi nawigacyjnych wyposażonych w urządzenia monitorujące ruch na szlaku żeglugowym oraz aktualne warunki nawigacyjne takie jak prędkość nurtu, temperatura i poziom wody. Uzupełnieniem systemu są sensory montowane na mostach umożliwiające pomiar prześwitu pod mostem oraz monitoring ruchu na szlaku żeglugowym.

W ramach rejsu realizowanego na szlaku żeglugowym Dolnej Wisły zaplanowane zostało rozmieszczenie pięciu boi oraz dwóch sensorów mostowych w lokalizacjach:

Boje:
Przegalina 936km Wisły
Grudziądz 834km Wisły
Bydgoszcz Fordon 774km Wisły
Toruń 725km Wisły

Włocławek 679km Wisły

Sensory:

Most Siennicki w Gdańsku

Most w Kieżmarku, 930km Wisły

W załączeniu przesyłam szczegółowy opis urządzeń wraz z rysunkiem technicznym. Jednocześnie zwracamy się do Państwa z prośbą o wsparcie w zakresie posadowienia w/w boi w ramach istniejących oznaczeń nawigacyjnych, w ramach możliwości regionalnych oddziałów i posterunków wodnych.

Z wyrazami szacunku,

Tomasz Markowski

Kierownik Grupy Badawczej Urządzeń Elektronicznych
Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Poznański Instytut Technologiczny

Załączniki

1. Specyfikacja techniczna boi i sensorów

Szczegółowy opis urządzeń Cristal z rysunkiem technicznym

Spis treści

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1. Inteligentna boja - wersja pilotażowa

(Opis dotyczy boi z oświetleniem aktywnym, ale jeśli boja będzie zakotwiczona na odcinku nie wymagającym takiego oświetlenia, wtedy nie zostanie ono zamontowane.)

Grafika 1: wygląd boi.

Grafika 2: przekrój poprzeczny boi.

Źródło: Powyższe grafiki zaczerpnięto z materiałów katalogowych producenta boi nawigacyjnych, firmy ROTO-TECH

1.1. Konstrukcja boi

Inteligentna boja w wersji pilotażowej powstaje na bazie produktu oferowanego przez firmę ROTO-TECH zwiualizowanego powyżej. Boja wykonana jest z tworzywa sztucznego (polietylen) i jest wypełniona styropianem. Posiada balast i okucia stalowe w części dolnej. Jest wybarwiona i posiada w części górnej znak nawigacyjny - stosowne do miejsca kotwiczenia: po lewej lub prawej stronie drogi wodnej.

Posiada także uchwyty transportowe.

1.2. Układy elektroniczne boi

Dodatkowo, wewnątrz pionowego słupka boi jest umieszczone zamknięte hermetycznie urządzenie elektroniczne małej mocy, odczytujące sygnały radiowe nadawane z urządzeń mobilnych umieszczonych na jednostkach pływających, pracujących w standardzie AIS. Urządzenie elektroniczne umieszczone na boi odczytuje własną pozycję geograficzną z sygnału radiowego GNSS. Urządzenie elektroniczne okresowo nadaje dane odczytane z czujnika umieszczonego w korpusie boi oraz z odebranych komunikatów AIS, wykorzystując przy emisji transmisję danych GPRS (obsługiwana przez sieć telefonii komórkowej GSM).

Czujnik umieszczony na boi to tzw. multisensor, mierzący okresowo odległość od dna w miejscu kotwiczenia boi, kąt pochylenia oraz temperaturę i prędkość strumienia wody opływającej boję, (Opisany pomiar prędkości, jest wykonywany tylko na jednej, ustalonej głębokości, w warstwie wody przy powierzchniowej).

1.3. Zasilanie boi

Urządzenie elektroniczne jest zasilane akumulatorem żelowym, zabudowanym wspólnie z elementami elektroniki w zamkniętej hermetycznie obudowie z tworzywa sztucznego.

1.4. Kotwiczenie boi

Zakłada się, że każda boja będzie kotwiczona do dna piaszczystego w rzece Wiśle, pełniąc funkcje: monitorującą oraz znaku nawigacyjnego jednocześnie. Elementy kotwiczenia to: kotwica stalowa typu Danforth 8 kg, krętlik, szekła, linka stalowa typu 6X19+FC d=10mm z uchem (rdzeń z włókna węglowego), ocynkowana lub nierdzewna.

2. Sensor prześwitu mostu z modułem komunikacyjnym

2.1. Układy elektroniczne sensora

Zespół elektroniczny mocowany na moście zawiera moduł komunikacyjny i składa się z urządzenia standardu AIS o nazwie Weatherdock ATON 3, posiadającego zintegrowany odbiornik GPS i realizujące komunikację AIS FATDMA/RATDM oraz z akumulatora żelowego z układem opcjonalnego ładowania akumulatora oraz z modułu sterowania cyklem pracy całego urządzenia. Urządzenie ATON wyposażone jest w antenę zewnętrzną 14cm.

Dodatkowo do dolnej ścianki stalowej szafki obudowy, zamocowany jest radarowy czujnik odległości niskiej mocy, z wiązką pomiarową skierowaną pionowo w dół, z kątem rozsyłu wiązki o maksymalnym kącie rozsyłu 6 stopni od pionu oraz o zasięgu pomiarowym maksymalnie 60m. Jego zadaniem jest określenie wartości (w metrach) prześwitu pod żeglownym przęsłem mostu i zwrócenie tej wartości w komunikacie urządzenia ATON.

2.2. Konstrukcja, wymiary i obsługa sensora

Wszystkie elementy urządzenia, oprócz anteny i końcówki czujnika radarowego - zamknięte są w szczelnej szafce stalowej i przeznaczone do zamocowania w pobliżu górnej części przęsła mostu, nad jego żeglowną częścią. Przykładowo mocowane wspornikami stalowymi do barierki mostu - podobnie jak mocowane są niektóre znaki nawigacyjne.

Urządzenie, przy dłuższym niż kilka dni, czasie użytkowania, wymaga ładowania akumulatora najlepiej realizowanego ze standardowej jednofazowej sieci elektrycznej 230V 50Hz, moc pobierana przez urządzenie to maksymalnie 8 Watów.

Wymiary obudowy bez anteny i czujnika (14 cm) wynosi 300mm x 300mm x 155mm. Masa urządzenia – w wersji z akumulatorem to 12 kg, w wersji bez akumulatora, zasilanej z sieci energetycznej - 6 kg

Annex II - Permission to place buoys on the lower Vistula River in Tczew

Tczew, dnia 16.04.2024 r.

GT.ZPH.5030.1.2024.TS

Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz
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Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie Zarząd Zlewni w Tczewie w odpowiedzi na wniosek z dnia 25.03.2024 r. (data wpływu 26.03.2024 r.) dotyczący zamontowania na rzece Wiśle pław wyposażonych w osprzęt pomiarowy przychyliła się do prośby.

Planowane jest wystawienie dwóch boi, gdzie jedna zostanie ustawiona w miejscowości Przegalina w km 936+000 a druga w miejscowości Grudziądz km 834+000.

Z uwagi na fakt, że pławy znajdują się na drodze wodnej na rzece Wiśle, należy przestrzegać poniższych warunków:

- Wystawione pławy będą w formie oznakowania nawigacyjnego pływającego w związku z tym dokładne miejsce ich wystawienia oraz każda późniejsza korekta musi być uzgodniona z przedstawicielem Zarządu Zlewni Tczew.
W związku z powyższym oznakowanie musi spełniać wymogi wynikające z rozporządzenia z dnia 28 kwietnia 2003 r. w sprawie przepisów żeglugowych na śródlądowych drogach wodnych (Dz. U z 2003 r., Nr 212, poz. 2072)
- Przed przejściem każdej wielkiej wody należy zebrać pławy
- W przypadku ewentualnego wykorzystywania w okresie temperatur ujemnych, pławy należy usunąć przed wystąpieniem zjawisk lodowych
- Każdorazowe wystawienie oraz usunięcie powinno zostać zgłoszone do przedstawiciela PGW WP
- Oznakowanie wraz z elementami kotwiącymi, powinno być stale oczyszczane z zanieczyszczeń, które niesie rzeka np. roślinność, gałęzie, drzewa itp.

Przedstawicielem PGW Wody Polskie Zarząd Zlewni w Tczewie będzie kierownik Bazy Flotylli Lodołamaczy Tomasz Skowroński – tel. kontaktowy 601612690.

DYREKTOR

Barbara Jezierska

Do wiadomości:

1. NW Tczew
2. a/a ZPH BFL

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Annex III - Permission to place buoys on the lower Vistula River in Toruń

Toruń, 10 kwietnia 2024r.

GR.ZPU.502.18.2024.ML

Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz
Poznański Instytut Technologiczny
Tomasz Markowski
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61-755 Poznań

Dotyczy: umieszczenia elementów systemu monitoringu czasu przewozów oraz warunków nawigacyjnych na rzece Wiśle w Toruniu km 725 oraz Fordonie km 774.

Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie Zarząd Zlewni w Toruniu w odniesieniu do Państwa pisma z dnia 25.03.2024 (data wpływu 26.03.2024), dotyczącego wyrażenia zgody na tymczasowe umieszczenie elementów systemu monitoringu czasu przewozów oraz warunków nawigacyjnych na rzece Wiśle w Toruniu km 725 oraz Fordonie km 774, informuje, iż przychyła się do Państwa wniosku.

Jednocześnie informujemy, iż w celu szczegółowego określenia lokalizacji i sposobu umieszczenia przedmiotowych elementów na szlaku żeglownym skontaktować należy się z Panem Jarosławem Wachowskim Kierownikiem Zespołu Wsparcia Technicznego jako jednostki zajmującej się utrzymaniem, oznakowaniem szlaku żeglugowego na rozpatrywanym odcinku – tel. 501 371 480 lub 56 306 71 63.

Z-CIA DYREKTORA
A. Markowska
Aneta Markowska

Otrzymują:

1. Adresat
2. ZPT Toruń
3. ZPU aa.

Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie
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e-mail: zz-torun@wody.gov.pl

www.wody.gov.pl

Annex IV - Permission to place buoys on the lower Vistula River in Włocławek

Włocławek, 18.04.2024 r.

WK.ZPH.503.1.2024.GW

Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz- Poznański Instytut Technologiczny
Tomasz Markowski
ul. Ewarysta Estkowskiego 6
61-755 Poznań

Dotyczy: umieszczenia monitoringu czasu przewozu oraz warunków nawigacyjnych szlaku żeglownego w km 679 rzeki Wisły.

W odpowiedzi na Państwa pismo wyrażamy zgodę na czasowe zainstalowanie w km 679 szlaku żeglownego rzeki Wisły (rejon mostu stalowego we Włocławku) boi nawigacyjnej z urządzeniami pomiarowymi służącymi do monitorowania ruchu na szlaku żeglownym oraz aktualnych warunków nawigacyjnych w ramach realizowanego projektu CRISTAL.

Deklarujemy wsparcie w zakresie pomocy w posadowieniu boi w ramach istniejącego oznakowania nawigacyjnego.

Osoba do kontaktu w przedmiotowej sprawie: Tomasz Radomski, tel. 54 233 93 95 w. 38.;
tomasz.radomski@wody.gov.pl

DYREKTOR

Piotr Feinlak

Otrzymują:

1. Adresat
2. a/a

Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie
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Annex V - Permission to place sensor devices on the Siennicki bridge in Gdańsk

Gdańsk, dnia 15.04.2024 r.

GZDIZ.IM.5003.1.14.2024.WE

**Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz -
Poznański Instytut Technologiczny
Tomasz Markowski
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61-755 Poznań**

Dotyczy: zgodny na umieszczenie sensora na Moście Siennickim

W odpowiedzi na Państwa pismo z dnia 25.03.2024 r. Gdański Zarząd Dróg i Zieleni wyraża zgodę na umieszczenie sensora na moście Siennickim w Gdańsku przy zachowaniu poniższych warunków.

Warunki lokalizacji sensora:

1. Wnioskodawca odpowiada za bezpieczeństwo użytkowników drogi związane z instalacją i eksploatacją sensora.
2. Montaż sensora zgłosić do Działu Obiektów Inżynierskich GZDIZ z 7 dniowym wyprzedzeniem (email: gzdiz@gdansk.gda.pl)
3. Sposób montażu sensora: za pomocą obejm do balustrad mostu. Nie dopuszcza się ingerencji w konstrukcję mostu. W przypadku uszkodzeń powłok antykorozyjny wykonać ich naprawy. W przypadku zmian w sposobie montażu, nowy sposób uzgodnić z Inspektorem GZDIZ t. 585 589 562
4. Instalowanie i eksploatacja sensora nie może ingerować w obowiązującą organizację ruchu. Należy zapewnić swobodne przejście dla pieszych.
5. Obiekt z uwagi na stan podpór (przyczółków) planowany jest do przebudowy. Obecnie trwa opracowanie opinii technicznej, która określi dalszy sposób eksploatacji obiektu, przez co zastrzegamy możliwość zmiany wyrażonej zgody.

Dodatkowo informujemy, że zarządcą rzeki Martwej Wisły w obrębie mostu jest Urząd Morski w Gdyni.

ZASTĘPCA DYREKTORA
ds. Infrastruktury i Remontów

Anna Bonkowska

Administratorem Pani/Pana danych osobowych pozyskanych w związku z prowadzoną korespondencją jest Gdański Zarząd Dróg i Zieleni z/s w Gdańsku, ul. Partyzantów 36. Pani/Pana dane osobowe będą przetwarzane w zakresie niezbędnym do prowadzenia korespondencji oraz w celach z niej wynikających. Ma Pani/Pan prawo dostępu do swoich danych osobowych, ich sprostowania, usunięcia lub ograniczenia przetwarzania, prawo do wniesienia sprzeciwu wobec przetwarzania, prawo do przenoszenia danych, prawo wniesienia skargi do Prezesa UODO. Szersze informacje o zasadach przetwarzania i ochrony Pani/Pana danych osobowych dostępne są pod adresem www.gzdiz.gda.pl

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ZASTĘPCA KIEROWNIKA
Działu Obiektów Inżynierskich
MEŁ
Włodzisław Elias

Annex V – Example of presentation for LL

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Annex VI - Survey scenarios

The “scenarios” may be tailored to each River Pilot’s conditions - as Polish example included

Business as usual scenario

During the **normal operation of the transport network**, the technologies developed in CRISTAL **will collect data from the IWW infrastructure & the river/channels** and make the results of the data analysis **available to the SCMS** through the DT.

SCMS is intended to be a product that will merge and assess the information collected **on river navigability** but also **on damage to the infrastructure**, so that, the SCMS user **will be able to see where and when inland navigation operations are affected**.

Navigational conditions data will be collected by **Smart Buoys** and **FOS**, so that it will be possible to assess whether there is **adequate water** depth on the river for transport, and **where shallowing is occurring** along a route. Increased sediment accumulation in critical sections of the waterway may cause reduced water depth and can lead to navigation hazards as well as increased dredging costs.

The **Digital Twins** developed based on the sensor technologies deployed in CRISTAL can provide a forecast of problems in the transport network in terms of river navigability and infrastructure availability (i.e. locks) making possible, for example, to predict the waterdepth of routes in the coming days based on analysis of data from upstream measuring devices.

The SCMS will also provide a feasibility assessment of planned routes that include inland navigation sections, and information on rail and road alternative routes, so that a planned route **including an inland navigation section can be re-planned** if any difficulties in the river emerge or are forecasted, based on the data analysis described above.

The SCMS will provide visibility of the 3 alternatives (road, rail, IWW) in terms of emissions, ETA (and feasibility in the case of IWW), thus allowing the system user to use the 3 modes in parallel if they wish, in line with the concept of synchromodality.

Polish example:

Monitoring the water level and the river bed for sediment is of particular importance for the operation of Polish rivers. Neither the Vistula nor the Oder has a RIS system, so monitoring river levels through alternative technologies such as Smart Buoys and FOS, which can provide information to the SCMS, is vital information fed directly to the logistics operator.

In this way, a logistics operator planning an inland waterway journey on the Vistula, for example, can assess the navigability of the route and, with the help of predictive tools such as DT, forecast the condition of the route in the near future. The information on navigability will allow the logistics operator to decide whether it is possible to execute an order in a given period.

At the same time, the SCMS functionality of determining the availability of alternative river routes provides information on the basis of which the operator can reschedule the voyage in the event of information on the unavailability of a route. In addition, the operator uses information about available other transport routes on a route similar to the Vistula, e.g. nearby railways or motorways. Thanks to the SCMS, he can assess which freight route, e.g. from Solec Kujawski to Gdansk, is of most interest to him - depending on whether he is focusing on the aspect of emissions reduction or the estimated time of delivery of the goods.

Please estimate the potential impacts of a system combining CRISTAL technologies, as listed below:

1. To what extent will the integrated system improve operational efficiency and achieve an 50% reliability target during disruptions (weather/human factors)?
2. What is the probability that the system will lead to at least a 20% modal shift to inland waterways?
3. What is the probability that the system will maintain at least 50% operational continuity during disruptions across the multimodal network?

Infrastructure failure scenario

In the present scenario, sensor technologies deployed in CRISTAL that can early **detect infrastructure damage (i.e. Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) and Acoustic Emissions (AE) technologies)**, detect early signs of damage to an infrastructure before extensive and possible irreversible damage occurs.

This information is then communicated to the infrastructure manager on order to timely carry out maintenance activities and **avoid the long-lasting lock or dam closure** which would happen if the damage evolved. At the same time, **this information will be communicated to the SCMS through the DT (which provides also an estimation of the closure duration for maintenance)**, making it possible to re-plan already planned routes that will be affected by the closure involving also the other transport modes if necessary to ensure continuity of operations.

Polish example:

The technologies developed in the project - designed to detect infrastructure damage early - can especially support critical points on river routes such as the Wloclawek dam on the Vistula, or the Lipki lock on the Oder.

Early detection of damage at the lock with AE or SIR technology would avoid a sudden lock failure and complete closure of the waterway on the Oder towards Gliwice, as was the case in November 2024.

At the same time, communicating lock closures via SCMS to the logistics operators using the lock would allow re-planning of the transport route. A prediction of the duration of the lock closure, which is available through DT, would allow the barge operator to decide whether to wait for the opportunity to pass through the lock to Gliwice or whether the route should be re-planned to another available port, e.g. Wroclaw. The SCMS functionality, which provides information on possible alternative waterways, but also on railways and motorways, would make it possible, in the event of infrastructure failure, to plan the use of other transport routes in the vicinity in accordance with the concept of synchronomodality.

Please estimate the potential impacts of a system combining CRISTAL technologies, as listed below:

4. Given an extreme weather event, what is the likelihood that the system maintains inland waterway navigability above 80%?
5. How much will the system improve navigability during infrastructure failure events?
6. How likely is the system to maintain 50% operational continuity in the logistics network during disruptions?
7. How likely is the system to increase the use of recycled materials by 30% in transport infrastructure?
8. How likely is the system to facilitate compliance with EU legislation during construction, maintenance, and operation of infrastructure (e.g., will it be easier to meet the legislative requirements for maintaining the technical conditions to which hydraulic structures should comply)?

Extreme weather event scenario

Also among the technologies produced at CRISTAL are Smart Buoys that **communicate with vessels**, which, on river routes where RIS does not function, can replace this system by providing information on **vessel movements to the SCMS**.

In addition, they are devices that indicate **changes in water level**, current speed and can be equipped with any sensors measuring environmental water parameters. In the event of a **change in water level, sudden rainfall**, increased current speeds could pose **risks for vessels**, potentially leading to accidents or difficulties in maneuvering. The information from these devices collected in the SCMS is intended to **monitor navigational conditions** on the river, and give information on the feasibility of transport in given sections.

Polish case example:

When technology such as SB is sited on the river, it measures both water parameters and vessel movements. In the event of unpredictable low water levels, such as in 2024 in the middle Vistula, the technology informs which section of the route is affected and where the navigability of the route may be impaired. The SCMS, through which this information is transmitted, simultaneously allows alternative river routes to be mapped, or shows

the availability of other modes of transport and transshipment points. In this way, if there is a disruption on the route due to a lack of navigability, transshipment of the cargo from inland waterway to rail can be planned and transport continuity maintained.

Please estimate the potential impacts of a system combining CRISTAL technologies, as listed below:

9. How likely is the system to reduce shipment waiting times in inland waterway transport by 80%?
10. How likely is the system to ensure 50% network functionality during weather- or human-induced disruptions?
11. How likely is the system to maintain efficient operations and ensure network functionality during weather- or human-induced disruptions?

Question for WP6 to be included validation of business model:

12. How much will the governance models that will be developed allow for the development of inter-institutional, international, or inter-modal cooperation?